

5+5 TWINNING AGREEMENT

Mohamed Cherif Messaadia
University, Algeria

Institute of Agronomic and Veterinary
Sciences (ISAV)

Laboratory of Animal Production,
Biotechnology and Health (PABIOS)

In partnership with

University of Gabes, Tunisia

Faculty of Sciences of Gabes (FSG)

Laboratory of Biodiversity and Valorization
of Bioresources in Arid Zones

1st ALGERIAN-TUNISIAN DAYS

**Biotechnologies for
Biodiversity, Healthy and
Sustainable Food**

1^{er} ATD BBHSF

22-23

October

2024

Book of Abstracts

Editor by:

Dr. Djalel Eddine GHERISSI

Dr. Houria OUENNES

Dr. Samir AYDI

Our Scientific Partner :

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Proceeding

1st ALGERIAN-TUNISIAN DAYS

1^{er} ATD

**Biotechnologies for Biodiversity,
Healthy and Sustainable Food**

BBHSF

22-23 October 2024

(Hybrid mode)

Dedication

Let us take a moment to honor and remember the dear colleagues: Prof. Djamel FADEL and Dr. Atef AOUADI who are no longer with us. Their dedication, passion, and contributions have left an indelible mark on our community. Though they have departed, their legacy continues to inspire us in our work. Let us keep their memory alive in our hearts as we move forward together, guided by the values they cherished.

May they rest in peace.

Chairman of the 1st Algero-Tunisian Days : BBHSF 2024

Dr. Djalel Eddine GHERISSI (Institute of Agricultural and Veterinary Sciences of Souk Ahras University)

Dr. Djalel Eddine GHERISSI, I am Algerian Assistant Professor specialist in Animal Production, biotechnology and health. I am the dumpty director of the Institute of Agricultural and Veterinary Sciences of Souk Ahras University in charge of the post-graduation, external relations and scientific research. I have many years experience in University teaching graduation, Master and doctoral levels in Veterinary and Agronomic Sciences and I am team leader at the research laboratory: Animal Production, Biotechnologies and Health. I am also an ex-researcher at the National Institute of Agricultural Research of Algeria. I give workshops in animal biotechnologies, animal health and genetic improvement of farm animals to train scientists, veterinarians, students, and farmers in improved livestock production practices. My current research is focused on livestock systems and production valorization and sustainability in particular under arid and semi-arid areas. The dairy cattle and the dromedary camel are the main focused species. My efforts in agricultural development are focused on improvement animal genetics, production and welfare. My long-term goal is to empower agriculturalists with the knowledge and skills needed to increase the production of nutritious animal-source foods as a means to reduce poverty, and improve food security.

Opening Ceremony Speech

With high annual population growth rates, increasing urbanization, and slow growth in domestic food production, the gap between consumption and domestic food production in the North Africa Region is likely to widen in the coming years (FAO 2022). Agricultural activities and livestock in the Maghreb countries remain vital resources for poor rural populations and a key source of income (FAO 2013). However, the key challenge ahead will be meeting the needs of a rapidly growing population while dealing with increasingly scarce natural resources and the growing impacts of climate change.

Agricultural practices, genetic diversity, land use changes, and climate impacts are deeply interconnected, requiring sustainable strategies that address both food security and biodiversity conservation. In this context, the question arises: how can the judicious application of animal and plant biotechnologies help balance nutritional needs, food security, health, and environmental preservation?

This symposium will explore the role of biotechnologies, both animal and plant-based, in the pursuit of sustainable food security. It will showcase the latest innovations in the field and examine how these advancements contribute to enhancing the resilience of food systems while tackling critical global challenges. Our primary goal is to identify strategic perspectives on leveraging biotechnologies to ensure long-term food security, while also maintaining environmental sustainability and promoting healthy living conditions.

These scientific days are a multidisciplinary platform, uniting researchers, industry experts, policymakers, and stakeholders from fields such as animal and plant sciences, biodiversity, food security, and health. The aim is to foster a comprehensive understanding of the role biotechnologies play in promoting sustainable food security and to facilitate meaningful discussions on how to maximize their benefits.

Objectives

This symposium aims to present advances in animal and plant biotechnologies that can enhance sustainable animal health, food security, and biodiversity conservation.

Focus Areas

- Biotechnologies applied to animal health and production
- Biotechnologies for agricultural productivity and sustainable vegetable crop production
- Biotechnologies supporting biodiversity and food security

Potential Topics

- Biotechnologies in Animal Husbandry (BAH)
- Food Safety: Biotechnological Approaches to Product Traceability (FS)
- Advancements in Assisted Reproductive Technologies for Livestock (ARTL)

- Genetic Characterization and Modification Techniques for Animal and Plant Improvement (GCMT)
- Biotechnology and Precision Agriculture (BPA)
- Biodiversity Preservation through Biotechnological Interventions (BPB)

Let us embark on this journey together to explore the transformative potential of biotechnologies in addressing the most pressing issues in food security, health, and environmental conservation.

Dr. Djalel Eddine CHERISSI

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Lectures' short Biography

Prof. Kamel Miroud is a Full Professor of Theriogenology at University of El Tarf, Algeria, specializing in animal reproductive health. With over 30 years of experience in teaching and research, Prof. Kame Miroud has made significant contributions to the field, focusing on reproductive physiology, assisted reproductive technologies, and fertility management in livestock. Their research spans topics such as reproductive pathologies associated with low herd fertility, reproduction management strategies, artificial insemination, embryo transfer, and reproductive endocrinology. Prof. Kamel Miroud has authored numerous peer-reviewed publications, mentored graduate students, and led several collaborative research projects aimed at improving reproductive efficiency in farm animals. They are also actively involved in professional veterinary organizations and serve as an advisor to industry partners on reproductive health strategies.

Dr. Samir Aydi, born in 1975 in Sfax, Tunisia, is an expert in plant biotechnology with a Doctorate of Science from the University of El Manar. He has held various academic roles, including ex-director of the Department of Life Sciences. His research spans plant physiology, biotechnology, and plant-microorganism interactions. He has supervised 28 advanced theses and published over 36 papers. Dr. Aydi coordinates national and international projects on crop resilience and biotechnology.

Dr. Djalel Eddine GHERISSI is an Algerian Assistant Professor specializing in Animal Production, Biotechnology, and Health. With extensive experience in teaching at various academic levels, he leads the research laboratory in Animal Production, Biotechnologies, and Health. His research focuses on livestock systems, particularly dairy cattle and dromedary camels, in arid regions. Dr. GHERISSI aims to enhance animal genetics, production, and welfare, empowering agriculturalists to improve food security through nutritious animal-source foods.

Prof. Lazhar Zourgui, a Full Professor at Gabes University, Tunisia, leads a research laboratory focused on *Opuntia* (cactus) biomolecules with beneficial activities, such as antioxidant, antidiabetic, anti-obesity, and anticancer effects. With a PhD in Biochemistry (1984) and a Doctorate of Science (1988), he has mentored 35 PhD and Master's students, authored 112 publications, and coordinated over six European projects. Since 2023, he has served as Research Coordinator for Cactus: Medicinal and Cosmetic Uses in FAO-ICARDA CactusNet.

Dr. Barour Djanette is a researcher and lecturer at the Institute of Agronomic and Veterinary Sciences at Souk Ahras University, Algeria. She is an Associate Professor specializing in veterinary microbiology and epidemiology of animal diseases. Her current research focuses on antibiotic resistance in various animal species. Previously, Dr. Barour served as the Head of the Veterinary Sciences Department and later as Deputy Director for Education at ISAV Taoura until the end of 2023. She has also worked as a veterinary inspector responsible for the epidemiological surveillance network and food hygiene and health control at the DSA in Souk Ahras.

Dr. Sameh Sassi Aydi is a plant physiology expert with a doctorate in Biological Sciences from the University of El Manar, Tunisia. Since 2011, she has held academic positions, including assistant professor and lecturer, and contributed to national and international research projects. Her work spans plant physiology, plant-microorganism interactions, and food product analysis. She has supervised 20 bachelor's and 14 advanced theses, with over 25 publications in related fields.

Dr. Sofiane TAMENDJARI is a lecturer in Food Safety Control, teaching Veterinary Medicine students. Their research focuses on dairy product safety, emphasizing quality control, contamination prevention, and regulatory standards to ensure consumer health. Dr. Dr. Sofiane TAMENDJARI is dedicated to advancing food safety practices in the dairy industry through education and research.

Dr. Rahmani Rami is a phytochemistry researcher specializing in bioactive plant compounds, with expertise in alkaloids, flavonoids, terpenes, and phenolic compounds. They earned a PhD in Biological Science from the University of Gabès and have contributed to

understanding the antioxidant, cytotoxic, and anti-inflammatory roles of plant secondary metabolites. Dr. Rahmani collaborates across disciplines, exploring phytochemicals' therapeutic potential, and mentors graduate students in natural product chemistry and phyto-pharmacology.

PLENARIES

5+5 TWINNING AGREEMENT : 1st ALGERIAN-TUNISIAN DAYS
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**Prof. Kamel MIROUD (Departement of Veterinary sciences, University of
El Tarf, Algeria):**

**Biotechnologies Animales : Moyens d'Amélioration des Productivités de la
Vache**

Abstract

Reproductive biotechnologies in cows encompass several techniques aimed at improving fertility, productivity, and health. These technologies play a fundamental role in modern livestock farming to meet the ever-growing global demand for dairy and meat products. Reproductive biotechnologies such as artificial insemination (AI), in vivo maturation (IVM), in vitro fertilization (IVF), in vivo embryo production (IVP), embryo transfer (ET), and gamete cryopreservation are essential for enhancing reproductive performance, preserving biodiversity, and advancing fundamental research. Research in this field will facilitate the use of assisted reproduction methods in both livestock and companion animals. IVF, IVP, and ET are powerful tools for studying fertilization and genetic material preservation.

Keywords: Animal Biotechnology, reproduction, Embryon transfer, Artificial Insemination, Invitro fecondation,

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Dr. Djalel Eddine GHERISSI (Institute of Agronomic and Veterinary sciences, University of Souk Ahras, Algeria) :

2024 the International Year of Camelids (IYC 2024): Reproduction Management and Artificial Insemination in Dromedary Camel

Abstract

The dromedary camel is a versatile species adapted to extreme arid conditions, serving various roles, including production, transport, and agricultural work. Its economic and social significance lies in its ability to sustain marginalized communities, largely due to the nutritional and therapeutic benefits of its milk and meat. In response to growing demand for camel products, there has been a shift towards the intensification of camel farming. However, the productivity of camel herds remains limited by factors such as low fertility rates, delayed puberty, extended inter-calving intervals, and low milk production, which hinder genetic progress and herd renewal.

To optimize reproductive performance and accelerate genetic improvement, it's essential to minimize unproductive periods like the waiting and reproduction periods. This can be achieved by adopting better farming systems, enhancing breeding practices, improving reproductive data recording and monitoring, and applying advanced reproductive techniques. Key strategies include managing sexual activity in both male and female camels and using artificial insemination (AI). Controlling ovarian cycles in female camels through follicular growth and ovulation timing is critical for inducing and synchronizing reproduction, particularly during off-seasons. While zootechnical methods alone are insufficient, pharmacological methods involving hormones like melatonin, progesterone, prostaglandin F_{2α}, and GnRH can help regulate reproductive cycles.

Research in AI for dromedary camels is focused on developing standardized sperm collection, quality monitoring, preservation techniques, and improving pregnancy rates. This biotechnology offers genetic, sanitary, and economic benefits, addressing fertility challenges related to short breeding seasons, long gestation periods, traditional reproductive practices, and reproductive diseases.

Keywords: Artificial insemination · Oestrus synchronization · Dromedary camel · Camel bull · Breeding · Reproduction performance · Sperm · Follicular cycle · Female camel · Calving interval

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**Dr. Djanette BAROUR (Institute of Agronomic and Veterinary sciences,
University of Souk Ahras, Algeria) :**

Analyses bactériologiques visant à déterminer la qualité du lait cru

Abstract

Le lait est un aliment biologique de choix , il contient les principaux éléments nécessaires à la croissance et au développement de l'organisme humain et animal , en particulier , les glucides , les lipides , les protéines , les vitamines et le calcium. Très favorable au développement des micro-organismes, dont certains sont dangereux du point de vue sanitaire et sont associés à des intoxications alimentaires causées par les Salmonelles, Yersinia enterocolitica, Listeria monocytogenes , Staphylococcus aureus et E coli entéro-hémorragique.

De ce fait une bonne qualité bactériologique du lait s'impose, ceci n'implique pas uniquement l'absence de germes pathogènes, mais aussi l'absence de substances inhibitrices tels que les résidus d'antibiotiques susceptibles de générer de graves problèmes de santé humaine et animale.

Cet atelier portera sur des aspects pratiques, visant à déterminer la qualité bactériologique du lait cru telle que définie par la législation Algérienne (Arrêté interministériel du 4 octobre 2016 fixant les critères microbiologiques des denrées alimentaires) ; à savoir la recherche de la flore aérobie mésophile totale , Staphylocoques à coagulase + , les Coliformes thermotolérants, Salmonella, Listeria monocytogenes et les antibiotiques .L'interprétation des résultats en satisfaisants ou acceptables est fondée sur les valeurs fixées pour ces critères bactériologiques.

Cet atelier devra permettre d'avoir une idée approfondie sur les techniques d'analyses adoptées afin de déterminer la qualité bactériologique de cette denrée précieuse, dont la contamination constitue un danger pour la santé publique et vétérinaire.

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Dr. Sofiane TAMENDJARI (Institute of Agronomic and Veterinary sciences, University of Souk Ahras, Algeria):

Contrôle sanitaire des carcasses à l'abattoir

Abstract

Nombreuses sont les maladies et affections pouvant touchées la santé de l'homme et de l'animal par le biais de l'alimentation qui est un élément essentiel pour le développement des sociétés et des pays. Prenant l'exemple de la viande, laquelle est un aliment important, parce qu'elle contient des nutriments essentiels pour le maintien des fonctions physiologiques, à l'amélioration de l'immunité et à la prévention de certaines maladies, notamment la malnutrition.

Mais lorsque cet aliment contient des produits chimiques non autorisés ou ne répond pas aux normes requises en matière de qualité nutritionnelle, de propriétés organoleptiques, de conservateurs alimentaires, d'agents pathogènes microbiens, de résidus de pesticides, de médicaments vétérinaires et de métaux lourds, des risques potentiels pour la santé du consommateur peuvent survenir.

Pour obtenir de la viande, une première transformation est requise, la mise à la mort ou l'abattage des animaux destinés à la consommation humaine et/ou animale, processus effectué dans des établissements notamment les abattoirs où a lieu un contrôle sanitaire de ces animaux avant et après abattage, constituent la première barrière protectrice de la santé du consommateur.

Dans notre workshop, nous essaierons d'aborder les principales techniques permettant d'effectuer un contrôle sanitaire des carcasses, afin d'identifier les dangers sanitaires et la conduite à tenir pour assurer la salubrité et longévité de cette denrée alimentaire.

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**Prof. Lazhar ZOURGUI (Laboratoire de recherche "Biodiversité,
Molécules, Application" Institut Supérieur de Biologie Appliquée
Médenine, Université de Gabès-Tunisie) :**

**Cactus active biomolecules and their use in cosmetics, agri-food, and
pharmaceutical**

Abstract

Opuntia species are used as local medicinal interventions for chronic diseases and as food sources, mainly because they possess nutritional properties and biological activities. Opuntia ficus-indica (L.) Mill, commonly known as prickly pear or nopal cactus, is the most economically valuable plant in the Cactaceae family worldwide. It is a tropical or subtropical plant, native to tropical and subtropical America, which can grow in arid and semi-arid climates. It belongs to the family of angiosperms dicotyledons Cactaceae of which about 1500 species of cacti are known. The Opuntia plant is distributed throughout the world and has great economic potential. There are differences in the phytochemical composition of Opuntia species between wild and domesticated species, and within the same species. It is an interesting source of plant bioactive compounds. Bioactives compound are compounds with nutritional benefits, and are generally classified into phenolic and non-phenolic compounds and pigments. Opuntia species are able to grow in almost all climates, for example, arid, temperate, and tropical climates, and their bioactive compound profiles change depending on the species, cultivar, and climatic conditions. Therefore, there is an opportunity for the discovery of new compound from different Opuntia cultivars. Health benefits of prickly pear are widely demonstrated: There is ample evidence of the health benefits of consuming prickly pear, due to its source of nutrients and vitamins and its antioxidant properties due to its content of bioactive compounds. In addition, prickly pear is used in the treatment of hyperglycemia and high cholesterol levels and its consumption is linked to a lower incidence of coronary heart disease and certain types of cancer. It may be effective in insulin-independent type 2 diabetes mellitus. Opuntia ficus-indica seed oil has shown potent antioxidant and prophylactic effects. Industrial applications of these bioactive compounds are increasing. In addition to their application in the pharmaceutical industries, bioactives compound are used in the food industry for the production of nutraceuticals, new food formulations (juices, drinks, jams, sweeteners). In my lecture, I will review in a comprehensive way the phytochemical, nutritional and bioactives compound composition of the different aerial and underground parts of Opuntia species. The biological activities and applications of Opuntia compounds are also discussed.

Keywords: cactus, biological activities, valorization, agrifood, actives biomolecules

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Dr. Sameh SASSI AYDI (Laboratoire de recherche : Biodiversité et valorisation des bioressources en zones arides. Faculté des Sciences à l'Université de Gabès, Tunisie).

Valorisation des bioressources en zones arides

Abstract

The process of biomass valorization consists of a variety of materials, including starch-rich food crops and waste (rice and maize), aquatic plants (such as algae), lignocellulosic plants (such as grass), animal waste, date-palm co-products and others. This process could be able to upgrade intermediate products to provide respectably desired product yields.

Three topics will be covered:

The first topic focuses on botanicals that have always been an important source of various food ingredients, particularly essential oils and other flavorings, their evaluation and valorization has become a topical issue for the researchers. Following this trend, the biorefining of chamomiles into fractions with different characteristics and uses was the focus of our investigation.

The second topic concerns cyanobacteria "Spirulina" which are free-living photoautotrophic organisms formerly known as blue-green algae and aims to the exploration of environmental, therapeutic, medical, and nutraceutical use of this microalga in intensive cultivation raceways.

The third topic synthesizes the most important aspects of palm waste re-use notably in soil less culture and its conversion into valuable biomolecules, together with waste from the food processing industry.

An overview of the state of the art, trends, concepts, feasibility, and problems in the subject of bioressources and waste valorization will be discussed during this conference.

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**Dr Rami RAHMANI (Institut Supérieur de Biologie Appliquée Médenine
Université de Gabès-Tunisie) :**

Bio Analyses phytochimiques: de l'extraction à la modélisation moléculaire

Résumé

The study focuses on the extraction, identification, and computational analysis of bioactive compounds derived from plant extracts. The extraction process utilized solvent-based techniques to isolate phytochemicals from the plant material, optimizing parameters such as solvent type, to ensure maximum yield of target compounds. The extracted samples were then subjected to High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC) for the identification and quantification of key bioactive molecules. HPLC enabled the separation of complex mixtures and provided detailed chromatographic profiles, allowing for the precise detection of compounds such as; phenolic acids and flavonoids.

Following the identification of bioactive molecules, *in silico* analysis was employed to predict the biological activity, molecular interactions, and pharmacokinetic properties of the compounds.

Three softwares will be used during the workshop, which are; Open Babel (for compounds conversion), PyRx (for molecular docking analysis), and Biovia (for data visualization). Furthermore, the web site Swiss Dock with consulting for ADME analysis.

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DAY 1

- 1. Biotechnologies in animal husbandry (BAH)**
- 2. Food safety (FS)**
- 3. Advancements in assisted reproductive technologies for livestock (ARTL)**
- 4. Genetic characterization and modification techniques for animal and plant improvement (GCMT)**
- 5. Biotechnology and precision agriculture (BPA)**
- 6. Biodiversity preservation through biotechnological interventions (BPB)**

ORAL COMMUNICATIONS

5+5 TWINNING AGREEMENT : 1st ALGERIAN-TUNISIAN DAYS
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Impact du cholestérol-cyclodextrine sur la congélation du sperme bovin dans un milieu à base de lécithine de soja

**DJEMOUAI Boukhalfa^{1*}, BENHENIA Karim², SAYAH Asmaa³, KOURAT Ahcene⁴,
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Résumé

L'insémination artificielle à l'aide de semence cryoconservée est l'une des biotechnologies les plus couramment utilisées chez les bovins. Son succès dépend toutefois de la qualité du sperme cryoconservé, qui peut être altérée par des dommages cellulaires causés par le choc thermique et le stress oxydatif. Cette étude vise à atténuer ces effets en traitant la membrane plasmique des spermatozoïdes avec du cholestérol solubilisé par les cyclodextrines. Pour cela, le sperme a été récolté sur 8 taureaux, puis mélangé et divisé en deux aliquotes : un témoin non traité et un autre traité avec du cholestérol encapsulé dans la cyclodextrine (CD-CHL) à raison de 2 mg pour 120 millions de cellules spermatiques, incubé à 22°C pendant 15 minutes. Après incubation, les aliquotes ont été diluées avec de la lécithine de soja (0,5 %), équilibrées à 4°C pendant 60 minutes, puis congelées dans l'azote liquide. À la décongélation à 38°C, l'aliquote traitée avec CD-CHL a montré des taux de motilité et de motilité progressive significativement plus élevés ($P < 0,05$), ainsi que de meilleurs paramètres cinétiques (VCL, VSL, VAP, LIN et BCF), et une meilleure intégrité de l'acrosome et de la membrane plasmique. En revanche, aucune différence significative n'a été observée en matière de peroxydation lipidique entre les deux aliquotes. En conclusion, la cyclodextrine chargée de cholestérol a prouvé son effet positif sur la cryoconservation du sperme de taureau dans un diluant à base de lécithine de soja.

Mots-clés : Intégrité de l'acrosome, intégrité de la membrane, mobilité, taureau.

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La perte de la gestation chez la jument: La mortalité embryonnaire comme exemple

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Résumé

La mortalité embryonnaire est l'une des majeurs problèmes de la baisse de fertilité chez la jument dans la région de Tiaret. Cela a été prouvé suite à un suivi de la gestation par échographie mené sur 197 juments de différentes races, 125 pur-sang Arabe, 26 Barbe, 21 Arabe-Barbe, 18 Pur-Sang, 4 Anglo-Arabe et 3 juments de selle appartenant au Haras National de Chaouchaoua et au Haras El-Mesk et des juments appartenant à des éleveurs privés de la région et sont mises à la reproduction durant toute la saison au Haras National Chaouchaoua et Haras El-Mesk. Notre suivi a débuté à partir du 13ème jour post-ovulation durant la saison de reproduction 2022 afin de mettre en évidence les différents facteurs qui peuvent favoriser la mortalité embryonnaire chez la jument. Le taux de mortalité embryonnaire obtenu durant les 45 jours post ovulation a été de 14.3% ; 5.5% des mortalités embryonnaires ont été diagnostiquées entre J13 et J20 post ovulation. Le taux de mortalité embryonnaire était plus élevé chez les juments barren 22.8%, les juments âgées plus de 16ans 15% et les juments mises à la reproduction au début de la saison (mois de février) 50%. Les juments à gestation gémellaire ont présenté un taux de mortalité embryonnaire plus élevé avec 37.5% des cas contre 9.1% chez les juments à gestation simple. Une modification de l'environnement utérin était également une cause d'une baisse de la fertilité se traduisant par un taux de mortalité embryonnaire élevé ; principalement, nous citons l'augmentation des liquides utérins anormaux qui ont conduit à un taux de 22.4% de mortalité embryonnaire. En conclusion, ces facteurs ont un impact économique non négligeable ; les identifier et comprendre leur influence sur la vie embryonnaire est indispensable pour limiter les pertes dans nos élevages équin.

Mots clés : Mortalité embryonnaire ; Age ; jument ; fertilité ; élevage

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Préservation de la race ovine Hamra en Algérie : réussite de la cryoconservation du sperme et de l'insémination artificielle

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Résumé

En Algérie, la race ovine Hamra est reconnue pour la qualité de sa viande et son adaptabilité aux milieux arides. Cependant, son effectif a fortement diminué ces dernières années, nécessitant la mise en place d'une stratégie de conservation. La cryoconservation et l'insémination artificielle sont des technologies qui peuvent contribuer à la préservation des races menacées de disparition. L'objectif de cette étude est de déterminer la qualité du sperme congelé en fonction de la saison chez la race Hamra, ainsi que la fertilité après insémination artificielle par voie cervicale. Pour ce faire, deux béliers de la race Hamra ont été utilisés pour des collectes mensuelles de semence, suivies d'une étape de cryoconservation et de stockage dans l'azote liquide. Des analyses spermatiques *in vitro* sur une période de 12 mois ont été réalisées après décongélation à 37°C. De plus, 25 brebis de la même race ont été inséminées artificiellement par voie cervicale après synchronisation des chaleurs. Les résultats ont montré que : i) la qualité optimale du sperme cryoconservé a été atteinte au mois de mars et ii) l'insémination artificielle avec ce sperme a permis d'obtenir un taux de gestation par échographie élevé de 80 %. En conclusion, la préservation et l'augmentation de l'effectif de la race Hamra sont faisables grâce à la réussite de la cryoconservation et de l'insémination artificielle.

Mots-clés : Sperme congelé, qualité du sperme *in vitro*, bélier, Echographie.

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The relationship between testes size, sexual behavior and sperm quality in Arabian stallions intended for Artificial Insemination

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Abstract

The aim of his study was to determine the reproductive efficiency of Arabian stallions presented at CNIAAG and elected for an artificial insemination (AI) program. Ten Arabian stallions between 8 and 15 years of age were subjected to an analysis of the reproductive parameters. Assessment of sexual behaviour, testicular measurements and appreciation of semen quality collected with the help of artificial vagina was done. There was a significant correlation between the sexual behaviour, the spermatic parameters and the testicular parameters, especially between the number of mounts with the motility and the daily sperm ejaculated (DSP) ($r=0.99$). The testicular volume total and mounts was highly correlated to the average volume of ejaculate (73.33 ± 60.27 ml) and total Sperm concentration (billions) ($r=0.99$) which allowed to produce 38 straws intended for the preservation. Based on the results, it is concluded that there is a positive correlation between (TSW) and motility, the various measurements of testis size were highly correlated with each other; and consequently to predict the fertility of the stallions from the testicular.

Keywords: Algeria; Arabian Stallion; Artificial Insemination; Reproduction.

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Developmental, behavioral and biochemical effects of anthracene and Pb⁺² to zebrafish embryos

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Abstract

This work aimed to determine the toxicity of anthracene and lead on the survival, development, and behavior of zebrafish (*Danio rerio*) eleutheroembryos. The OECD guideline (TG 236) was used to perform fish embryo toxicity (FET) experiments. Moreover, acetylcholinesterase activity (AChE) was investigated as a biomarker of neurotoxicity. The video monitoring device Zebrabox® (Viewpoint, France) was used to assess the effects of these chemicals on the behavior of 120 hpf larvae. According to obtained data, both chemicals have a moderate toxic effect on fish embryo survival: Pb⁺² 96h-LC50 value was 76.51 mg/L. Anthracene 96h-LC50 value was 133.35 mg/L. No significant developmental malformations were observed for both chemicals. In term of behavior, Anthracene decreased total swimming distance (TSD) and total swimming time (TST) in light and dark periods at concentrations of 3.2, 6.4, 12.8 and 25.6 mg/L, indicating hypoactivity. However, Pb⁺² affected locomotion by increasing distance travelled in rapid movements after 120 hpf exposure at 0.1, 1 and 10 mg/L suggesting hyperactivity. Furthermore, after 120 hpf exposure, AChE was not responsive nor sensitive to Pb⁺² and anthracene, suggesting that effects at the neuronal level manifested in locomotion impairments are not mediated by the disruption of AChE.

Keys words: PAHs, Biomarkers, Behavior, FET, Lead, AChE and development.

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Hepatoprotective effect of sandfish “*Scincus scincus*” extract on cadmium-induced hepatotoxicity in rats

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Abstract

Hepatotoxicity is defined as injury to the liver or impairment of the liver function after exposure to various risk factors. This study was planned to investigate hypothesis of hepatoprotective effect of sandfish (*Scincus scincus*) consumed for its health virtuous by local Saharan peoples from Algeria. For this purpose, sandfish extract benefits against cadmium chloride (CdCl₂)-induced liver toxicity in rats was evaluated. The rats (n=23) were divided into 4 groups; the control group (n= 5) received a vehicle, the extract group (n= 5) received via gavage sandfish extract (100mg/kg), Cadmium group (n= 6) received CdCl₂ (1 mg/kg, intraperitoneal injection), cadmium +extract group(n= 7) received after the single injection of CdCl₂(1mg/kg) the sandfish extract (100 mg/kg, orally).The experimentation was performed over 56 days. Body weight, relative liver weight (LW) and biochemical parameters namely glucose, triglycerides, cholesterol, alanine aminotransferase (ALT), aspartate aminotransferase (AST), total bilirubin (TB) and direct bilirubin (DB) were measured. Glutathione (GSH) and Malondialdehyde (MDA) activities were measured to evaluate the changes in antioxidative system and lipid peroxidation activity in liver tissues. Relative LW, MDA, ALT and TB were significantly increased by CdCl₂ treatment. The treatment with sandfish extract after CdCl₂ injection reduced significantly ALT, AST and TB. The GSH level was significantly altered (0.19±0.05 mg/g) by Cd treatment, which was recovered (0.43±0.08 mg/g) after that by sandfish extract gavages. In conclusion, inclusion of sandfish in rat diet showed significant evidences of hepatoprotective effect in response to acute Cd hepatotoxicity.

Keywords: Biochemical parameters, Cadmium, GSH, Hepatoprotective effect, *Scincus scincus*

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Freezing of human sperm: comparative study on sperm parameters, activation of caspase 3 and mitochondrial membrane potential

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Abstract

In this study we compared vapor freezing technique to vitrification of human sperm, while assessing their effects on sperm parameters by CASA system, the rate of activation of caspases 3 and the mitochondrial potential ($\Delta\Psi_m$) using flow cytometry either in the presence or the absence of 2.5mg/ml of Acetyl-L Carnitine (ALC). We reported that cryopreservation causes a significant decrease in sperm parameters (motility, velocity, vitality and morphology) compared to fresh sperm. The addition of ALC caused a significant improvement in motility, velocity and vitality for both techniques. ALC supplementation has also improved the percentage of typical forms of spermatozoa after vitrification. The study of the apoptotic markers after cryopreservation in the presence of ALC showed a significant increase in the mitochondrial membrane potential after slow freezing . No significant change in the rate of active caspase 3 after slow freezing and vitrification have been reported. Acetyl -l -carnitine could help protect the mitochondrial membrane potential against oxidative stress caused by the EAO which improve mobility and vitality of sperm.

Keywords: Slow freezing, vitrification, activated Caspase3, mitochondrial potential, Acetyl-l-carnitine.

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Protective Effects of Ginger Oil (*Zingiber officinale*) against Neurotoxicity Induced by Maneb in Adult Rats: behavioural, biochemical and histological approaches

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Abstract

Background: The widespread use of maneb in agriculture has raised concerns about its potential health and environmental risks. Epidemiological evidence suggests a link between maneb exposure and an increased risk of neurodegenerative diseases

Objective: Hence, this study aimed to investigate the neuroprotective effect of ginger oil of subacute exposure to maneb by the intraperitoneal route on hippocampus function in rats and the effect of ginger oil on brain function biomarkers, compartmental and histological approach.

Methodology: Adult female rats were assigned into four experimental group. The first group consisted of negative controls. The second group represented the positive controls where mice received daily, via gavage, ginger oil at a dose of 50 mg/kg. The third group, rats were subjected to intraperitoneal injections of maneb (30 mg/kg BW). The fourth group (MB+GO) received daily the same dose of maneb as group 3 along with ginger oil at the same dose as group 2.

Finding: Our findings demonstrated that ginger oil treatment mitigates oxidative stress by restoring redox balance, reducing lipid peroxidation (MDA) and protein oxidation (PCO) levels, and enhancing the activity of antioxidant enzymes SOD and CAT in the hippocampus of adult female rats. Phenotypically, maneb exposure induced neurobehavioral impairments, as evidenced by a decreased discrimination index in the novel object recognition test (NORT) and a significantly reduced number of marbles buried in the marble burying test (MBT),

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suggesting increased anxiety-like behavior. Our study provides compelling evidence that ginger oil can effectively reverse these anxiety-like behaviors and oxidative stress in adult rats

Conclusion: Taken together, ginger oil, which is subject to fewer regulations than traditional medications could be used as a dietary supplement to improve brain health and could be a promising nutraceutical choice.

Keywords: Ginger essential oil; maneb; Neurotoxicity; Impairment of behavioral function, Histological analysis.

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How does the production system affect the *longissimus lumborum* muscle proteome of dromedary camels (*Camelus dromedarius*)?

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Abstract

Proteomics has been widely used in domestic animal science, particularly in meat science, over the past decade. However, studies on dromedary meat proteomics are very limited. This study characterizes the *longissimus lumborum* muscle proteome of male *Sahraoui* dromedary camels from two different production systems (extensive versus intensive) using a label-free proteomics approach. Samples were taken from six camels with similar body weight and nutritional conditions from southern Algeria. A total of 1,405 proteins were identified in the muscle proteome, with 40 showing differential accumulation. The proteome characterization reveals similarities with domestic ruminants, with most biological process annotations related to catalytic activity (32.8%) and binding (16.7%). Production systems influenced several metabolic pathways. In the extensive system group, there was an increased accumulation of energy metabolism and contractile apparatus proteins such as MYBPC1 and MYL2, likely due to the need for dromedaries to move in search of food in extensive rangelands. Conversely, the intensive system group showed an increase in proteins related to amino acid and lipid metabolisms (ACAT1 and ACAA2), likely as a result of the higher growth rates and nutritional levels in the intensive system. These findings help distinguish between the traditional extensive production system and the intensive production system.

Keywords: Camel Husbandry, Proteomics, *Longissimus Lumborum*, El Oued

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Variations des paramètres sanguins chez la chèvre Arbia pendant la lactation et la période de tarissement

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Résumé

En Algérie, les éleveurs s'intéressent de plus en plus à l'élevage des chèvres en raison de la forte demande de leurs produits par les consommateurs. L'importance nutritionnelle du lait de chèvre est bien connue, tout comme l'intérêt pour la viande des chevreaux. La chèvre Arbia est l'une des races les plus populaires pour la production de lait et de viande. Il est donc important de conserver et de contrôler la santé des chèvres afin d'augmenter la production animale. Cependant, ces dernières années, de nombreuses recherches ont montré que les paramètres sanguins des petits ruminants étaient influencés par de nombreux facteurs tels que l'âge, les conditions climatiques, la race et les stades physiologiques de la production. Le but de cette étude était d'étudier les variations de certains paramètres biochimiques et minéraux sanguins pendant la lactation et la période de tarissement chez les chèvres Arbia dans les zones arides du Sud de l'Algérie. Dix chèvres Arbia en bonne santé (âgées de 12 ± 0 mois) ont été choisies dans une ferme de la commune de Sidi Okba (dans la wilaya de Biskra). Le sang a été prélevé une fois chez chaque chèvre à la 3^e semaine (début de la lactation), à la 8^e semaine (milieu de la lactation) et pendant la 2^e semaine de la période de tarissement. Le glucose plasmatique (Glu), le cholestérol (Chol), les triglycérides (TG), l'urée, la créatinine (Créat), le calcium (Ca), le phosphore inorganique (Pi) et le magnésium (Mg) ont été mesurés. Les niveaux plasmatiques de Chol, d'urée et de minéraux (Ca, Pi et Mg) n'ont pas été significativement affectés par les différents stades de la lactation et de la période de tarissement des chèvres Arbia. Au milieu de la lactation, le Glu a enregistré le niveau le plus bas par rapport au début de la lactation et à la période de tarissement. Par rapport au début de la lactation, les TG ont augmenté ($p < 0,05$) et la Créat a diminué ($p < 0,05$) pendant la période de tarissement. En conclusion, les résultats obtenus aideraient certainement les éleveurs et les vétérinaires cliniques à contrôler la santé et l'état nutritionnel des chèvres Arbia dans les zones arides d'Algérie afin d'augmenter la production animale.

Mots-clés : Chèvre Arbia, paramètres sanguins, lactation, période de tarissement, Algérie.

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Development of a new dietary supplement with high antioxidant and anti-diabetic potential

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Abstract

The search for new substances from natural resources capable of reducing or regulating blood sugar levels has become increasingly important in recent years, leading to the emergence of several reports indicating the significant activity of natural agents.

It is in this context that our study focuses on the antioxidant and anti-diabetic potential of a new natural dietary supplement composed of numerous active ingredients; as well as its protective effect on pancreatic, hepatic and renal cells in diabetic rats.

Variations in the parameters of liver and kidney toxicity in the different groups (control, diabetic and treated) were highlighted by the study of biochemical parameters and confirmed by a histopathological study of the pancreas.

This dietary supplement corrected glycemic parameters from 2.82g/l to 1.27g/l, enzymatic parameters such as superoxide dismutase (SOD) and catalase (CAT) and glutathione peroxidase (GPX), with good defense against the hepatotoxicity (AST, ALT, LDH) and nephrotoxicity (albumin, urea, creatinine) of diabetes, as well as good antioxidant status and histopathological protection.

The pancreas of diabetic subjects shows necrotic islets with cellular atrophy, particularly of β -cells; whereas in treated subjects a moderate protective action was observed, which can be explained by increased expression of antioxidant enzymes; and inactivation of TNF- α and consequent reduction in circulating free radical levels, allowing better chelation of NO before it reaches β -cells and damages them. The partial protective effect of this dietary supplement on pancreatic β -cells prevents a reduction in insulin levels.

This study adds value to our natural product, which has demonstrated powerful hypoglycemic and antioxidant effects, paving the way for therapeutic and pharmacological applications.

Key words: dietary supplement, diabetes, antioxidant.

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Assessment of the viability and survival of free and encapsulated

***Lactobacillus plantarum* s10 in simulated buccal-gastro-intestinal conditions**

using food matrices as probiotic carriers

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Abstract

Due to the increasing prevalence of milk allergies, juices containing beneficial bacteria such as probiotics present a promising solution to address this issue. This study evaluates the viability and survival of *Lactobacillus plantarum* S10 under simulated oral-gastrointestinal conditions, focusing on the impact of food matrices, specifically strawberry and cucumber juices, as probiotic carriers. The primary objective is to assess the survival rates of free and encapsulated bacteria through different digestive stages. We specifically investigated how these juices influence the viability of *Lactobacillus plantarum* S10, comparing their performance in free and encapsulated forms. Preliminary results indicated that encapsulated bacteria exhibited a survival rate of 70% after exposure to gastrointestinal conditions, while free bacteria showed a survival rate of 40%. The antioxidant properties of phenolic extracts from strawberries and cucumbers were also analyzed to determine their effect on probiotic viability. By examining the interactions between the food matrices and the probiotic bacteria, this research aims to identify effective strategies for enhancing the delivery of beneficial probiotics in the gastrointestinal tract, contributing to the development of functional foods with improved health benefits.

Keywords: Probiotics, *Lactobacillus plantarum* S10, Juices, Gastrointestinal Survival, Bioactive Compounds.

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Evolution of the biochemical Profile and body condition score according to cow performance at the postpartum period

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Abstract

This study investigated the evolution of body condition, daily milk production, and select biochemical profiles in relation to performance in Montbeliard dairy cows raised in semi-arid conditions. Blood samples were collected monthly from 74 clinically healthy dairy cows in semi-intensive herds over three months postpartum. Body condition score (BCS), feed consumption (FC), and reproductive events were recorded. Plasma levels of albumin, urea, glucose, total cholesterol, calcium, phosphorus, and magnesium were analyzed using colorimetric methods specific to each parameter.

The cows were categorized into four performance classes: low-performing, average-performing, productive, and highly productive. Productive cows had an average daily milk yield of 22.5 kg, average-performing cows produced 15-17 kg, and low-performing cows produced 12 kg. A one-way repeated measures analysis of variance (ANOVA) revealed a significant effect of performance on biochemical profiles and body condition.

Productive cows exhibited a rapid decline in body condition during early postpartum, followed by a swift recovery. In contrast, low-performing cows had significantly lower serum levels of urea, total cholesterol, magnesium, and phosphorus compared to the other groups.

These results suggest that postpartum nutrition, as assessed by body condition and metabolic profiles, provides valuable insights for reproductive monitoring. It also helps explain factors contributing to poor reproductive performance, such as conception rate at first insemination, coital index, and the interval between calving and mating.

Keywords: BCS, biochemical profile, dairy cattle, performance, semi-arid, postpartum.

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Food security a Green approach: Comparative Study of the Chemical Composition and in vitro Bioactive Potential of tree Essentials Oils from Lamiaceae plant against germs causing bovine mastitis

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Abstract

In recent years, antimicrobial resistance has posed a real challenge for food safety officials, primarily caused by the misuse and excessive use of antimicrobials to treat, prevent, or control infections in humans, animals, and plants. Furthermore, with an impact on the health of animals and plants, reducing the productivity of farms and threatening food security. In this context, the development of new antibacterial agents has become a priority. Therefore, the aim of this work is to investigate the chemical composition of two essential oils obtained from *Origanum vulgare* (OVEO) and *Mentha spicata* (MSEO) using Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry (GC-MS). Additionally, *In vitro* screening the antibacterial activity of EOs and determine the minimum inhibitory and bactericidal concentrations against germs causing bovine mastitis: standard and clinical strains of *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli*. After drying and extraction of essential oils by hydrodistillation, GC/MS analysis identified 55 compounds from (OVEO), for elements were predominant; γ -Terpinene (27.11%), followed by Thymol (22.11%), o-Cymene (13.91%), Carvacrol (13.83%). for (MSEO) 90 compounds are identified, with two elements are predominant; D-Carvone (39.43%) and D-Limonene (32.21%). For the first method of antimicrobial activity, EOs inhibits all isolated bacteria with great sensitivity for (OVEO) and medium sensitivity for (MSEO). However, for the second test EOs have a bacteriostatic action against the germs tested. The results showed that the EOs studied constituted a promising alternative for the control of the pathogens studied and for the prevention of bovine mastitis and they represent a biodegradable resource for environment.

Keywords: *bovine mastitis, antimicrobial activity, in vitro, Origanum vulgare, Mentha spicata.*

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Identification of lactic acid bacteria isolated from goat's milk and evaluation of their technological characteristics

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Abstract

Milk is a staple food for all consumers. In most cases, the term "milk" refers to cow's milk and many people assume it is good. However, goat's milk is even richer and more beneficial. Goat's milk is particularly attractive due to its unique composition, which has led it to be considered as a high-quality raw material only for the manufacture of food intended for certain segments of the population with specific needs (the elderly and infants)

The present work is a contribution to the identification and evaluation of the technological properties of lactic acid bacteria isolated from raw goat milk from the Jijel region. The isolation was carried out on MRS medium and 12 isolates were selected by using morphological, physiological and biochemical tests. The phenotypic identification of the isolates revealed the presence of the following genera (Lactococcus, Pediococcus, Streptococcus, Enterococcus, Leuconostoc and Lactobacillus).

The results of the evaluation of the technological aptitudes indicate that most of the isolates present a good acidifying and proteolytic power, but a weak lipolytic power.

Keywords: Biochemical tests, Lactic acid bacteria, MRS, Goat's milk, Technological skills.

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***In vitro* evaluation of the pathogenicity of avian pathogenic *Escherichia coli* isolates from Algerian poultry farms.**

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Abstract

Avian colibacillosis is an infectious disease with a worldwide geographical distribution, causing considerable economic losses and threatening the poultry sector. The causative agent of this disease is the pathogenic avian *Escherichia coli* APEC.

The aim of the present study is to assess the pathogenicity of APEC circulating in Algerian poultry farms.

APEC were isolated from organs of chickens with lesions indicating colibacillosis. Various biochemical screening tests were carried out. Pathogenicity of isolates was demonstrated by adherence test carried out by plating on Rouge Congo Agar (RCA) medium and hemolytic activity test was carried out by spot test on fresh blood agar (5%).

A total of 100 isolates were obtained, of which 92% showed a black aspect on RCA medium, confirming their exopolysaccharide production and consequently their ability to adhere and produce biofilms. 08% of the isolates showed a green halo, indicating partial degradation of red blood cells, signifying that these isolates are α -hemolytic.

These results are to be expected as the isolates were obtained from chicken organs, which means that most of the isolates have the ability to adhere to different tissues, which is considered to be the first stage of infection. The low haemolytic activity observed in our isolates can be explained by the fact that they were not isolated from blood samples.

The results obtained in our study are interesting and requires molecular tests to detect virulence factors in our isolates.

Keywords: colibacillosis, pathogenicity, adhesion, biofilm, hemolysis

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Lice of Domestic animals: prevalence and identification by mass spectrometry (MALDI-TOF/MS)

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Abstract

The identification of lice is based either on morphological characteristics or on molecular aspects, a technique which remains expensive.

On the other hand, there is a fast, easy, reliable and inexpensive technique which is MALDI-TOF/MS based on the comparison of protein profiles.

This technique has been used to identify several arthropods, but has not been used for the identification of lice to date.

For this purpose, we collected lice on domestic animals (cattle, sheep, goats and horses) in two regions of North-Eastern Algeria, in this case, the region of Souk Ahras and Guelma, and identified them by the MALDI-TOF/MS technique.

799 lice were collected from cattle, 103 lice from sheep, 237 lice from goats and 84 from horses. Morphological identification of lice under binocular magnification revealed 3 species in cattle, 2 species in sheep, 2 species in goats and a single species in horses (*Damalinia equi*).

Identification by the MALDI-TOF/MS tool revealed correct spectra (same profile and reproducible) especially for the species: *Linognathus africanus*, *Damalinia caprae*, *Damalinia bovis* and *Haematopinus eurysternus*.

For other species, the technique revealed incorrect spectra.

MOTS CLES : Lice ; Identification ; MALDI-TOF/MS ; Souk-Ahras ; Guelma

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Understanding Genetic Variability in Sheep Reproduction for Better Resource Management in Algeria

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Abstract

The reproduction of sheep breeds in Algeria is vital to the country's agricultural production and food security. However, this reproduction is influenced by various genetic factors that need to be thoroughly understood to optimize the management of genetic resources. This study focuses on analyzing the genetic factors affecting the prolificacy of local sheep breeds in Algeria.

Prolificacy, defined as a ewe's ability to give birth to multiple lambs in a single reproductive cycle, is a key factor in the efficiency and profitability of sheep production systems globally. Understanding the genetic basis of prolificacy is essential for improving reproductive performance and flock productivity. This study employs a methodology that includes chip genotyping, whole genome sequencing, and functional analyses to identify and characterize the genes associated with prolificacy. Key candidate genes such as the bone morphogenetic protein receptor 1B (BMPR1B), bone morphogenetic protein 15 (BMP15), growth differentiation factor 9 (GDF9), β -1, 4-N-acetylgalactosaminyl transferase 2 (B4GALNT2), and leptin receptor (LEPR) have been identified as major contributors to prolificacy in sheep.

The first mutation associated with increased fecundity in sheep (FecB) was discovered in the BMPR1B gene, which is now a crucial fertility marker in many breeds. Although some breeds rely on other major genes or combinations for fertility, the selection and improvement of sheep reproductive performance often depend on phenotypic characteristics. Since the 1980s, the discovery of major genes affecting prolificacy in sheep has grown, and DNA tests have become essential for utilizing these genes to determine the genetic basis of high prolificacy in diverse breeds worldwide.

Keywords: Prolificacy ; Major Genes ; Sheep ; Fertility

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Polysaccharides from *Moringa oleifera*: therapeutic insights and safety features functional food. In vivo study and improvement kidney damage

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Abstract

Moringaoleifera, a plant with a rich ethnopharmacological history, has gained attention for its potential therapeutic properties. Polysaccharides derived from *Moringaoleifera* have demonstrated various biological activities, including antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and nephroprotective effects.

This study aimed to evaluate the therapeutic efficacy of *Moringaoleifera* polysaccharides (MOPs) on kidney damage in an animal model in alleviating BPA-induced nephrotoxicity.

The experiment included control rats and rats treated with Bisphenol A administered orally by gavage (50 mg/kg bw), MOP(100 mg/kg) or their combination during 30 days. At the end of the experimental period, 24 h urine volumes, plasma and kidney tissue, were collected for biochemical and histological analysis.

Our research demonstrated that BPA-exposure led to increased lipid peroxidation, as indicated by elevated malondialdehyde (MDA) levels in the kidneys of treated rats, along with significant rises in plasmatic urea and creatinine levels. Additionally, BPA administration resulted in decreased activities of key antioxidant enzymes, including catalase, glutathione peroxidase, and superoxide dismutase, while also glutathione and vitamin C levels decreased. However, treatment with MOPs effectively mitigated kidney dysfunction by reducing oxidative stress markers and improving renal histopathology.

These findings suggest that the natural compounds found in MOPs could serve as promising therapeutic agents for protecting kidney health against the harmful effects of BPA exposure.

Keywords: Polysaccharides of MO, Antioxidant properties, Bisphenol A, nephrotoxicity, rats.

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Sheep biodiversity management in Algeria: Analysis of genetic polymorphisms of prolificacy

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Abstract

Sheep biodiversity in Algeria is rich and varied, with 12 breeds well adapted to local conditions. However, uncontrolled crossbreeding is leading to the dispersion and erosion of the genetic capital of these breeds. In sheep breeding, prolificacy is a crucial technical and economic factor for increasing profitability and sustainability. Although this trait has low heritability from a genetic point of view, specific mutations with a significant impact on increasing the number of ovulations and prolificacy have been discovered in four fertility genes (Fec genes): FecB/BMPR1B, FecG/GDF9, FecX/BMP15, and FecL/B4GALNT2. Our study aims to analyze the polymorphism of these genes associated with prolificacy in different Algerian sheep breeds. It also seeks to determine whether there is an association between the polymorphisms of these genes and the level of prolificacy in these breeds, while identifying potential mutations that could improve prolificacy. To carry out this study; we plan to conduct field surveys and representative sampling of each breed. We will phenotype the different breeds sampled, collecting morpho-biometric data such as sex, weight, animal dimensions, wool characteristics, and reproductive properties, including fertility and prolificacy rates. Genotyping of the different breeds sampled will be carried out by extracting and purifying total DNA from blood samples using the sodium

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chloride (NaCl) technique. We will then examine the polymorphism of the main genes involved in sheep prolificacy using various molecular biology techniques, such as PCR-RFLP, allele-specific PCR, and possibly sequencing, to look for potential causal mutations in these genes and their influence on sheep prolificacy rates. The expected results of this study will provide new data to improve the management of Algerian sheep populations, particularly in areas where major mutations affecting prolificacy are present.

Keywords: Biodiversity, Prolificacy, Genetic polymorphism, Fertility genes, Algerian sheep

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Biotechnology Meets Climate Change: A Comprehensive Study mapping

THI Influences on AI Success Rates in mediterranean climate

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Abstract

The Mediterranean basin, especially the North African region, is highly sensitive to climate change. Heat stress, often measured by the temperature-humidity index (THI), negatively impacts the reproductive performance of dairy cows. This study aims to evaluate the relationship between insemination success and fertility of dairy cattle under different THI levels in coastal areas. Data were collected from 71,270 artificial inseminations between 2016 and 2021, including dates of first AI, subsequent inseminations, pregnancy diagnoses, and reproductive periods. According to a logistic regression model with a 74.4% prediction accuracy, a rise in THI is linked to lower insemination success ($B = -0.959$, $P < 0.001$). We observed a reduction in fertilizing inseminations by 17.5% and 15% under moderate and severe heat stress, respectively. The rate of non-fertilizing AI was significantly higher during heat stress (72.29%, 73.26%, 75.42%, and 75.98% for non-heat stress, light, moderate, and severe heat stress, respectively). Additionally, elevated THI significantly reduced the conception rate at the first artificial insemination (CR1stAI) ($P < 0.001$), with a 41.7% and 38% reduction for moderate and severe heat stress, respectively, compared to non-heat stress conditions. The fertility index (FI) was 1.84 ± 0.897 , and higher THI was correlated with increased FI ($P < 0.001$). Heat stress significantly affected the services per conception, increasing by 0.036 for each THI point ≥ 68 . The interval from the first to the last

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insemination (IFL) also varied significantly with the THI at the first AI, showing 55 and 59 days for $THI < 72$ and $THI \geq 72$ ($P < 0.001$), respectively. The IFL increased by 1.334 days for each THI point ≥ 68 . This study underscores the detrimental effects of climatic conditions on dairy cattle fertility and highlights the urgent need for strategies to mitigate these impacts, particularly by improving dairy cow welfare.

Keywords: artificial insemination, heat stress, fertility, conception at first artificial insemination, services per conception, IFL.

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Animal feed in difficult periods in the context of integrated soil-plant-animal systems in Algeria

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Abstract

A study carried out in the form of a survey on the optimisation of animal feed based on traditional knowledge in integrated soil-crop-livestock systems in the wilaya of Ain Defla. The aim of the survey was to identify these systems, which are little known to most farmers. While livestock farming plays a crucial role in the economy and food security, traditional livestock farming systems are often faced with the challenges of food resource shortages, soil degradation and low animal productivity.

Farmers were interviewed on a single occasion using Google Forms. Data processing was carried out using Google Forms for the single-variate statistical analysis and SPSS IBM Statistics for the multivariate statistical analysis, with all the variables being categorical and qualitative. This study enabled us to identify three (3) main systems or groups: i) group A, which dominates with more than 52% of respondents having a semi-intensive farm and an area of 5 to 10 Ha, ii) group B with 34% of farmers having a semi-extensive farm and areas of less than 5 Ha, iii) and group C with 14% of farmers having a traditional extensive farm without land or soil.

In these systems, mainly in groups B and C, we noted the use of certain traditional skills and unconventional livestock feeding in situations of emergency.

Keywords: Animal feeding, integrated soil-crop-livestock system, traditional knowledge.

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Azolla: A Cost-Effective Alternative Feed for Livestock

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Abstract:

Finding easily accessible and reasonably priced substitute sources has become essential for breeders trying to cut costs associated with animal production, as a result of the scarcity of concentrates and green fodder, as well as their high costs in animal feed and the low economic productivity in some countries due to increased import costs.

The goal of this study is to investigate *Azolla pinnata's* nutritional potential as animal feed. *Azolla* is a tiny aquatic fern that floats freely and can be found all over the world. *Azolla pinnata* was grown in a water trough for this, harvested, and sun-dried. *Azolla* sample that had been sun-dried was examined for proximate principles. *Azolla* had a dry matter content of 5.13%. 80.52% of the dry matter was found to be organic matter overall. These consist of 41.20% nitrogen free extract, 4.5% ether extract, 13.9% crude fibre, and 24.51% crude protein.

There was 16.98% total Ash content. *Azolla* is a rich source of vitamins, trace minerals, and crude protein, *Azolla* is therefore regarded as potential unconventional feed for livestock.

Keywords: Animal production, *Azolla pinnata*, dry matter, livestock, protein.

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Les facteurs de risque de la brucellose chez les humains en Afrique du

Nord: Revue systématique

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Abstract

La brucellose est une maladie zoonotique due à des bactéries du genre *Brucella*. Malgré la mise en œuvre de différentes stratégies de lutte contre cette pathologie chez les ruminants dans les pays au sud du bassin méditerranéen, malheureusement, nous constatons qu'elle sévit toujours sous forme enzootique dans cette région. L'objectif principal de notre analyse systématique de la littérature est de d'identifier les principaux facteurs de risque de la brucellose chez les humains, entre 2010 et 2023, dans les pays d'Afrique du Nord.

Le processus de sélection des articles, appliqué aux bases de données *PubMed*, *ScienceDirect* et *Google Scholar*, par la méthode *PRISMA* (1), a permis d'extraire à partir de 18 études éligibles, des données sur la taille de l'échantillon, le nombre de cas positifs et les facteurs de risque prédominants associés à la brucellose dans la région Afrique du nord. Des analyses statistiques à l'aide du logiciel *Excel* ont été réalisées afin de déterminer l'effet des facteurs de risque sur la séroprévalence associés à l'infection à *Brucella*. Les odds ratios (OR) et leur intervalle de confiance à 95 % ont été calculés.

Notre étude a permis d'indiquer que la séroprévalence de la brucellose est significativement plus élevée chez les humains de sexe masculin que chez les féminins (OR : 1.26, IC à 95% : 1.06 – 1.50) et chez les humains de plus de 35 ans (OR : 1.24, IC à 95% : 0.94 – 1.63). De plus, les éleveurs (OR : 1.01, IC à 95% : 0.48 – 2.14) et les employés d'abattoir (OR : 0.98, IC à 95% : 0.46 – 2.07) avaient un risque plus élevé de contracter la maladie. En ce qui concerne la résidence, nous avons trouvé que les gens qui vivent à zones rurales (OR : 1.59, IC à 95% : 1.24 – 2.04) sont plus susceptibles d'acquérir la maladie que les zones urbaines (OR : 0.62, IC à 95% : 0.48 – 0.80). Les gens qui consomment les produits laitiers crus (OR : 2.28, IC à 95% : 1.93- 2.70) et qui sont en contact avec les animaux d'élevage (OR : 1.62, IC à 95% : 1.44- 1.83) ont un risque plus élevé d'avoir la brucellose.

Ces résultats suggèrent la nécessité d'appliquer un plan de lutte régional, car les mouvements irréguliers entre les frontières peuvent accroître le risque de transmission de la brucellose d'un pays à un autre.

Mots clés : Brucellose, ruminants, séroprévalence, facteurs de risque, Afrique du Nord.

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Diagnostic et traitement des mammites de la vache laitière par les vétérinaires de terrain en Algérie

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Les mammites engendrent des pertes économiques directes et indirectes particulièrement lourdes. La réduction de l'incidence de cette pathologie est donc une démarche essentielle en matière de conduite d'élevage.

L'objectif de cette étude est de mettre en évidence les principaux critères qui déterminent la réalisation d'un diagnostic de mammites et ceux qui conduisent le choix d'un traitement.

En matière de pathologie mammaire comme pour les autres pathologies, un diagnostic précis est indispensable pour établir une démarche thérapeutique et permettra également de sélectionner les méthodes de prévention, qu'elles soient sanitaires ou médicales, les plus appropriées. Sa qualité et sa précision sont donc primordiales.

Mammites-Diagnostic-Traitement- Vache laitière

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L'impact de la supplémentation en acide organique sur la production laitière des vaches laitières : REVUE SYSTEMATIQUE

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Résumé :

La production laitière est une activité économique importante dans de nombreux pays du monde. Les éleveurs de vaches laitières sont constamment à la recherche de moyens d'améliorer la productivité de leurs animaux. L'incorporation des acides organiques dans l'alimentation des vaches laitières est une stratégie qui a été étudiée pour son potentiel d'améliorer le rendement laitier.

Cette revue systématique de la littérature cherche à évaluer l'impact de l'addition d'acides organiques, tels que l'acide malique et l'acide propionique, dans l'alimentation des vaches laitières sur leur rendement laitier. Cependant, notre étude s'appuie sur des études antérieures qui ont été publiées dans des bases de données académiques (Pub Med, Google Scholar, Science direct). Au total, 8 études ont été retenues pour être incluses dans cette revue systématique et étude de méta-analyse après une sélection rigoureuse et selon des critères stricts. L'analyse des résultats a montré que, dans certaines études, le rendement laitier était plus élevé pour les vaches supplémentées en acide propionique ou en acide malique. Les augmentations respectives étaient de 4,66 % et de 6,12 %. Dans d'autres études, la production laitière n'était pas affectée. Cependant, l'hétérogénéité entre les études souligne l'influence potentielle d'autres facteurs sur les résultats. En conclusion, l'incorporation des acides organiques dans l'alimentation des vaches laitières peut augmenter le rendement laitier, mais l'effet n'est pas systématique. Cette stratégie peut donc être rentable pour les éleveurs, mais elle doit être évaluée au cas par cas.

Mots clés : acide malique, acide propionique, vache laitière, acide organique, production laitière.

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Effect of the incorporation of date scraps on the fattening performance of Ouled Djellal lambs in a semi-arid environment (North-East of Algeria)

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Abstract

Livestock sector is important to the economy of North African countries, The study focused on a study of growth-fattening of lambs, product of the test on 100 Ouled Djellal ewes, divided into two batches, raised in steppe pastures in North-East of Algeria, 50 females were supplemented with 400g/animal/day in scraps of dates Hchaf Ghars. The effect of this supplementation was estimated based on their reproductive performance. This is how 3 batches of lambs received rations based on increasing proportions of hchaf Ghars date scraps (0R%, 23%R and 46%R). The effect of these rations was estimated on their weight growth and consumption.

The results showed the best ADG and live weight at fattening were recorded in lambs having received 46% rejects in their rations. The latter were the most effective since they recorded the lowest consumption index (8.02).

Scraps dates (Hchef Ghars) can therefore constitute an economically interesting alternative energy source to replace imported barley and thus contribute to national autonomy and the profitability of the production of red meats in arid regions.

Keywords: Date scraps, growth, production, lambs.

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Prevalence and Risk Factors of Bovine Subclinical Mastitis on Conventional Dairy Farms in Northeast Algeria

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Abstract

Background: The dairy sector in Algeria faces various challenges, including a high prevalence of diseases in herds, especially mastitis. However, studies on the prevalence of mastitis, especially in the eastern region of Algeria, are rare. Thus, this study aims to assess the prevalence of subclinical mastitis and its associated risk factors in northern Algeria. **Methods:** **Methodology:** The study included 61 dairy cows from three farms in the Souk Ahras region. The California Mastitis Test (CMT) and visual inspection were used to determine the prevalence of subclinical mastitis. **Result:** The overall prevalence at the cow level was 75.4% (46/61) for subclinical mastitis cases. At the neighborhood level, the prevalence of subclinical mastitis cases was 38.93% (95/244). The study revealed that lactation stage and age were significant intrinsic risk factors for mastitis ($P < 0.05$). In addition, dry cow treatment were extrinsic risk factors for mastitis ($P < 0.05$). Given the high prevalence of mastitis in this region, regular screening and appropriate treatment are essential to reduce the risk of mastitis and improve cow health. **Keywords:** Subclinical mastitis, Prevalence, Risk factors, Dairy farms.

Keywords: Subclinical mastitis, Prevalence, Risk factors, Dairy farms

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Analysis of the reproductive performance of imported dairy cows raised in a hot Mediterranean climate in Algeria

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Abstract

Production cost management remains a major challenge and a key factor in assessing the competitiveness gap between farms, regions, and countries. The objective of this study was to evaluate the reproductive performance of 20 imported cows, consisting equally of the Montbéliarde and Prim'Holstein breeds, raised in a semi-intensive production system under a Mediterranean climate. Meteorological data collected between 2012 and 2017 in Guelma region revealed that the average monthly values of ambient temperature (AT), relative humidity (RH), and temperature-humidity index (THI) ranged between $18.79 \pm 6.33^{\circ}\text{C}$, $71.41 \pm 18.84\%$, and 63.42 ± 8.44 , respectively. The analysis of the results showed that the age at first mating for the herd was 21.17 ± 4.49 months and that at first calving was 30.76 ± 4.58 months. Although not significant, this period was shorter for Prim'Holstein cows (20.50 ± 5.70 vs. 21.84 ± 3.04 months and 29.47 ± 5.69 vs. 31.92 ± 3.65 months, respectively). For the other parameters, although most were below the recommended standards, most results favored the Montbéliarde breed. The calving-to-calving interval ranged, depending on the calving order, between 16.60 ± 5.56 and 20.09 ± 4.55 months for the herd, and between 15.74 ± 5.23 and 20.09 ± 4.55 months for Montbéliarde, and between 17.82 ± 6.20 and 22.03 ± 4.76 months for Prim'Holstein. The observed increase in this criterion is mainly due to the extension of the calving-to-conception interval. At the same time, fertility and numerical productivity rates showed statistically significant differences in favor of the Montbéliarde breed ($p < 0.05$). In conclusion, mastering reproductive management, particularly early heat detection and heat induction techniques, is essential for improving the productivity of imported cows breeds raised in a semi-intensive production system under a hot climate.

Keywords: cows; Prim'Holstein ; Montbéliarde; climate ; reproductive performance

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Pregnancy-Related Changes Of The Blood Biochemical Profile In Ouled Djellal Ewe's Breed Under Semi-Arid Conditions (Algeria)

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Abstract

In mammals, the pregnant female carries many physiological and anatomical changes. Biochemical profiles are very important tools for monitoring gestation progress. This study was designed to investigate pregnancy-related changes of blood metabolites in Ouled Djellal ewes under semi-arid conditions. Blood samples were collected from ten non pregnant multiparous ewes 4 weeks before conception and 4, 12 and 18 weeks of pregnancy age. The pattern of changes of some biochemical parameters were studied. Cholesterol level showed no significant changes during pregnancy, while triglyceride, AST and Ca decreased up to the 12th week of pregnancy, whereas the total protein, albumin, and creatinine increased toward the 12th week of pregnancy. Urea reached maximum levels at the end of the pregnancy, contrary to ALT that was significantly decreased. Glucose concentration showed a continual decrease varying from 2.08 ± 0.78 g.l-1 at the first month of pregnancy to 0.35 ± 0.36 g.l-1 at the 18th week of pregnancy. On the other hand, pregnancy establishment increased significantly the glucose, triglyceride, albumin, and urea, but it decreased significantly the cholesterol and creatinine levels. No differences were observed between pregnant and non-pregnant ewe for the rest of the parameters. These results demonstrated clear evidence of pregnancy-related distribution of blood biochemical indices of Ouled Djellal ewe under semi-arid conditions. Some substrates and enzymes were

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mainly higher during the first half of pregnancy (triglyceride, AST and Ca), and some others increased from the mild pregnancy period (total protein, albumin and creatinine), while urea and ALT changes were observed at late pregnancy. The energetic demand increased with advancing pregnancy.

Keywords: blood biochemical parameters; ewe; pregnancy; prior to mating; semi-arid area

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Artificial intelligence application in Animal Management

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Abstract

Recent advancements in animal management, particularly with the integration of technology and artificial intelligence, have significantly contributed to the development of productive animal management. Many researchers are incorporating technology into herd management to optimize production. This review aims to compile recently utilized technologies in animal management across various areas, including health, production, and reproduction. In the realm of animal health, researchers are focusing on the early detection of issues through continuous monitoring of parameters such as respiration, heart rate, weight, food and water intake, reticular motility, and ruminal pH variations. These measures help identify various pathologies and afflictions, with a specific emphasis on mastitis, addressing it promptly to prevent economic losses. Reproduction studies predominantly center on estrus detection, utilizing both visual and non-visual detectors. Technologies based on body temperature variations, including rumen, vaginal, ear skin temperature, and ventral tail base, have gained prominence due to their effectiveness and minimally invasive nature. Additionally, sound recognition methods and mobility detectors, such as tail mobility, stress detectors, and pedometers, contribute to estrus detection. In the context of milk production, various systems, including animal identification, weighing, and monitoring behavioral changes, have been studied in order to enhance animal production.

Keywords: Animal, Artificial Intelligence, Estrus, Health, Production, Technology.

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REPRODUCTION OF A TELEOSTIAN FISH THE BOOPS BOOPS BUG IN THE EASTERN ALGERIA NORTH

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Abstract

The present work aims to contribute to a better knowledge of the biology of a fish from the sparidae family Boopsboops (Linnaeus, 1758). The study of the biology of the bug was carried out on 906 individuals and makes it possible to highlight the characteristics of the reproduction of our species by studying: The sex ratio which shows an annual average value of 48.89% (for the year 2014), 48.30% (for the year) in favor of males. The monthly fluctuations of the Gonado-somatic ratio RGS which informs us about the period of reproduction of the bug in the Skikda region, which extends between January-May and that the sexual cycle Boopsboops goes through four successive phases. The study of the Hepato-somatic ratio RHS, and the reserves of mesenteric fats allowed us to conclude that the reserves of mesenteric fats are not the origin of the gonadal energy reserves and that our species draws the hepatic reserves to meet the energy expenses caused by reproduction. The determination of the size of the first maturity made it possible to remember that the females reach sexual maturity rather compared to the males at the average height ($L_t = 13\text{cm}$) and the males at the average height ($L_t = 14\text{cm}$).

Keywords: Boopsboops, biology, reproduction, gulf of Skikda.

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Reproductive cycle of the Sardine *Sardina pilchardus* (Walbaum, 1792) in the bay of Collo (Algerian East coasts)

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Abstract:

A study on a sexual cycle of *Sardina Pilchardus* in Algerian East coast (bay of Collo) was carried out on 469 specimens during 2014/2015. The study of the annual sex-ratio averages, shows that the females dominate with a SR = 37.78%. *Sardina pilchardus* is spawning over an extended period from November to March with peaks in the coldest months. The evolution of the gonado-somatic report shows that the reproductive cycle consists of four successive phases; a phase of slow maturation, a phase of significant sexual activity, a phase of emission of the sexual products, finally a phase of sexual rest. The monthly variations of the hepto-somatic report inform us that the liver didn't have any role in the transfer of lipid reserves necessary for vitellogenesis which confirm theranking of our fish among fatty fish. The first sexual maturity is reached fora fish at total length Lt = 11,5cm for the two sexes. The variations of the mesenteric reserves inform us that the minimum values are recorded during the coldest months. The condition factor allows us to deduce that the sardina of the bay of Collo don't stop eating during the laying period and that the energy contributions are stored for reuse later in various physiological activities.

Keywords: *Sardina Pilchrdus* ;bay of Collo; Reproductive cycle; Sexual maturity;Gonado-Somatic report.

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Variation of physiological, inflammatory and hematological parameters in a murine model of experimental asthma

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Abstract

Clove has long been used for therapeutic purposes and many studies demonstrating its composition rich in bioactive compounds agree to attribute multiple virtues to it. In our present study, we chose the aqueous extract of this plant to highlight its *in vivo* properties, particularly in a murine experimental asthma model. Our experiments were carried out with the aim of firstly evaluating the effects of the administration of the aqueous extract of the plant *Syzygium Aromaticum* in order to evaluate the physiological parameters (variation in body weight, absolute and relative weight of the lungs). Secondly, the aim was to confirm the anti-inflammatory protective potential of the plant by measuring hematological and inflammatory parameters (FNS, serum IL-4).

The results of the weight study showed that asthmatic and treated rats (OVA+ECQ) reached a value higher than the asthmatic group (OVA) (35.68g). Regarding the absolute and relative lung weight, there was a highly significant decrease ($1.24 \pm 0.43g$; $0.64 \pm 0.22g$) in OVA+ECQ rats, compared to OVA rats ($1.82 \pm 0.24g$; $0.94 \pm 0.14g$). This effect of reducing lung weight is due to the decrease in the presence of inflammation in this organ. Regarding the changes in the inflammatory response triggered by OVA treatment, there was a significant increase in the total number of lymphocytes in these rats. However, there was an improvement in these rates in OVA+ECQ rats in the form of a decrease in the levels of white blood cells and lymphocytes. For the variation in the level of IL-4 in serum, there was an increase (2.5 pg/ml), in asthmatic rats. In contrast, treatment of these rats with the aqueous extract improved the concentration of IL-4 (1.9 pg/ml).

Thus, our study showed that the anti-inflammatory effect of the plant helped protect and improve the damage caused by allergic asthma in rats treated with the plant. These improvements are reflected in a restoration of hematological parameters (FNS, IL-4).

Keywords: Asthma; *Syzygium Aromaticum* ; FNS; IL-4; absolute weight and relative weight.

Le sperme epididymaire chez le dromadaire : caracteristiques, methode de collecte et cryoconservation

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Résumé

La reproduction efficace est l'objectif recherché pour l'amélioration durable de la productivité animale à l'aide des biotechnologies appliquées à la reproduction. Certaines mesures sont importantes lors du choix du dromadaire mâle reproducteur. Tenir compte de l'aspect saisonnier de la reproduction chez cette espèce ; la saison du rut en Algérie dure de novembre à mars avec un pic en décembre. Le sperme du dromadaire mâle se caractérise par sa nature visqueuse (présence d'un gel épais qui se liquéfie lentement plus de 90 min), Les difficultés de collecte du sperme de mâles agressifs en rut nous a obligé de collecter les spermatozoïdes de l'épididyme qui est une technique importante dans la génération et la conservation de cette espèce. On collecte les gonades du dromadaire dont l'âge est plus de 6 ans après son abattage. La collecte du sperme épидидymaire se fait par plusieurs méthodes mais la technique de rinçage rétrograde (Retrograde Flushing) reste la plus utilisée. Les échantillons obtenus ont été évalués pour leur volume, leur concentration en spermatozoïdes, leur motilité totale et progressive, leur viabilité et leur morphologie. Les échantillons présentant une motilité progressive $\geq 75\%$ et une concentration minimale de 200×10^6 spz/mL ont été dilués à une concentration finale de 100×10^6 spz/mL et une composition finale de dilueur à base de Tris. Après 1,5 h d'équilibration à 4 °C, les échantillons ont été encore dilués pour atteindre la concentration finale de 4 % de glycérol et de 50×10^6 spz/mL. Après 1,5 h supplémentaire à 4°C, les échantillons ont été chargés dans des paillettes pré-refroidies de 0,5 ml, placées pendant 15 min à 4 cm au-dessus du niveau d'azote liquide, puis plongées dans l'azote liquide. Les paramètres de motilité ont été évalués à 37°C, grâce à un Analyseur de sperme assisté par ordinateur (CASA). Il n'y a pas de consensus sur un dilueur approprié à utiliser avec le sperme de dromadaire, bien que de nombreux dilueurs aient été évalués et que les tampons Tris aient été considérés comme satisfaisants. La conservation à court terme du sperme de dromadaire à 5 °C a donné lieu à un très petit nombre de grossesses et les issues de grossesse du sperme cryoconservé sont extrêmement faibles. Le sperme de dromadaire peut être dilué en utilisant une grande variété de dilueurs, notamment le citrate - jaune d'œuf -Tris. Cependant, la motilité des spermatozoïdes diminue dans les 24 à 48 heures de stockage à 4 °C. La cryoconservation du sperme de dromadaire n'a pas donné de résultats satisfaisants et des études supplémentaires sont nécessaires.

Mots clés : caractéristiques, analyses, épидидyme, sperme et dromadaire.

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Study of genetic and phenotypic diversity in Algerian indigenous chicken breeds

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Abstract

“PRIMA SCALA-MEDI” project is focusing on genetic and phenotypic characterization of, as well as on adaptability research for, local breeds of sheep and chickens of the Mediterranean region. It is a multi-country project implemented in three North African (Tunisia, Algeria, Morocco) and two Southern European (France, Italy) countries. As to the chicken species, which is found in Algeria, the project comprises two parts: the first one is directed towards the description of the local populations’ diversity and the second one is aimed at the development of crossbreeding between two contrasting origins of local chickens. A field survey was carried out among more than 100 farms located in five distinct agroecological and climatic regions of the country to further understand the local chicken populations and the farming practices. Data relating to farming practices, morphobiometric, and zootechnic indicators were accumulated during these surveys. In addition, biological samples in the form of blood were collected from each individual bird for molecular analyses, for instance, DNA-chip-assisted genotyping and epigenetic analyses using the LUMA technique. In total, 250 birds were sampled – 200 females and 50 males. ... The last group of 100 chickens were taken from the breeding institute of ITELV, who have been in a closed colony for more than 10 years, without any crossbreeding with exotic strains. Following the DNA isolation, the DNA of the samples was analyzed using IMAGE001v2 DNA array (approx. 10k SNPs). Quality checking measures, Fst values and Principal Components Analysis (PCA) confirmed that the animals from the two ITELV centres, Baba-Ali and Tlemcen, and the village chickens from northern Algeria were genetically distinct. This differentiation is more likely caused by genetic drift or inbreeding among the closed ITELV herds. Respondents also mention that most of the farm management is done by females, and the chickens had different forms. The local chickens, however, demonstrated considerable genetic variation and low genetic structuring of diversity in geographical athletic climatic zones.

Keywords: Scala Medi, Chicken, farmer, ITELV, Algeria, Phenotypic, Genotypic Diversity.

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Évaluation des Effets Insecticides et Biochimiques de l'Extrait Foliaire de *Hyoscyamus albus* sur le Rat Wistar

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Face à la réglementation croissante sur les pesticides de synthèse, l'exploration des extraits végétaux comme alternatives naturelles a pris de l'ampleur. Certains végétaux, capables de synthétiser des composés toxiques, sont utilisés comme insecticides botaniques. Nous avons mené une étude sur l'efficacité insecticide de l'extrait foliaire de *Hyoscyamus albus*, une plante reconnue pour ses propriétés médicinales, sur des rats Wistar. L'objectif était d'analyser l'impact de cet extrait sur les paramètres biochimiques des rats, traités pendant 7 jours.

Les résultats montrent que l'extrait aqueux de *H. albus* influence significativement les taux de créatinine, triglycérides et cholestérol, et induit une hypoglycémie chez les femelles. Les composés bioactifs présents dans l'extrait semblent offrir des propriétés anti-inflammatoires, antioxydantes, anti-diabétiques et hypolipidémiques.

Mots-clés : Rat Wistar, *Hyoscyamus albus*, paramètres biochimiques.

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Microscopic Study of the Cloacal Bursae of Broiler Chickens during IBD in Algeria Area

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Abstract

Algeria has recently witnessed an unprecedented spread out of the infections bursal disease virus (IBD). This has consequently aroused a heated debate among poultry industry professionals. Preliminary observations have shown that the cloacal bursa (BF) is the most sensitive organ to the virus. Therefore, this work is an attempt to study the microscopic appearance of the cloacal bursa during IBDV infection. 120 broilers (ISA 15) , were taken from two chicken coops ; clinically healthy broilers were taken from the first coop and used as a control sample. Broilers with pathognomonic lesions of IBD were taken from the second coop. The study has shown that the cloacal bursa is the most sensitive organ to pathological stress of IBDV (Infectious Bursal Disease Virus) and that the macroscopic appearance illustrates three phases; A phase of fast hypertrophy during days 3 and 4 post infection, followed by a two-day quick-involution phase and another relatively slow involution phase that runs from day 6 to day 8 post infection; A state of atrophy is reached then. The study has also shown that, IBDV infections produce histological lesions mostly in the lymphoid tissues such as the bursa of Fabricius, thymus, and spleen; Degeneration and necrosis of lymphoid B cells; especially the medulla of the bursal histological unit (follicles) were observed.

Keywords: Broiler chickens; Cloacal bursa ; IBD ; Microscopic appearance ; IBDV

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Situation actuelle de la contamination des denrées alimentaires par les mycotoxines en Algérie.

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Résumé

La contamination mondiale des denrées alimentaires et des aliments pour animaux par des mycotoxines pose un problème de santé important. Parmi les nombreuses toxines, un groupe de composés hautement toxiques, appelés mycotoxines, mérite une attention particulière. Les mycotoxines sont des composés toxiques naturels produits par certains types de moisissures. Les effets des mycotoxines d'origine alimentaire peuvent être aigus ou chroniques. Les mycotoxines agricoles les plus importantes comprennent la fumonisine, le déoxynivalénol, l'ochratoxine A, la zéaralénone et l'aflatoxine (AF). Ces dernières font partie des mycotoxines les plus toxiques. Il ne peut jamais y avoir de garantie absolue que nos aliments sont sains. Théoriquement, chaque pays dispose d'une agence qui supervise la sécurité alimentaire et réglemente les niveaux acceptables de contaminants inévitables. Les principaux produits alimentaires largement consommés par les Algériens proviennent de l'importation. Au Journal officiel algérien, la réglementation parle, mais brièvement, des mycotoxines. De nombreuses études sont en cours pour détecter les aflatoxines, mais elles restent insuffisantes. Il est nécessaire de préparer un plan d'action national pour le contrôle des mycotoxines, au moins dans les produits largement consommés.

Keywords: Mycotoxines, Santé Publique, Réglementation, Algérie.

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***Diplectanum aequans* (Metazoan, Platyhelminths) gill parasite of
Dicentrarchus labrax (Linnaeus, 1758) (Teleostei, Moronidae) off the
Algerian coast**

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Monogenea is a group of parasitic flatworms primarily known as ectoparasites and commonly infest aquatic hosts, particularly fish. The presence of Monogenea on fishes can induce significant pathological changes in the host, especially in the gills and skin, leading to impaired respiratory function and overall health.

In this study, we focus on Monogenean parasite of *Dicentrarchus labrax* (Linnaeus, 1758) off the Algerian coast. The examination of the gills of 30 fish, allowed us to identify 35 parasites belonging to the class of Monogenea. The morpho-anatomical analysis revealed the presence of a single parasitic species *Diplectanum aequans* (Wagener, 1857) Diesing, 1858, which is distinguished by a specialized attachment organ called the haptor. This parasite is classified under the subclass Monopisthocotylea (Odhner, 1912), and the family Diplectanidae.

Keywords: Monogenea, Monopisthocotylea, *Diplectanum aequans*, *Dicentrarchus labrax*
Algeria.

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Phage therapy as an effective control strategy of multidrug resistance avian pathogenic *Escherichia coli* (MDR- APEC) strains

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Abstract

The misuse of antibiotics for the treatment and the control of avian colibacillosis has led to an increase in antimicrobial resistance (AMR) and the emergence of avian pathogenic *Escherichia coli* (APEC) strains with high multidrug resistance properties. Because of the potential zoonotic risk of APEC strains via the food chain and the transfer of virulence and resistance genes from APEC to the other extra intestinal pathogenic *Escherichia coli* (exPEC), MDR- APEC strains constitute a serious concern for public health. Biosecurity measures and vaccines were not sufficient to protect birds against avian colibacillosis, therefore new control strategies are needed to decrease the impact of APEC strains, phage therapy is a promising approach to combat bacterial infections, including multidrug-resistant bacteria. This work, as a synthesis of previous works, attempts to present the most up-to-date on phage therapy against multidrug resistance avian pathogenic *Escherichia coli* (MDR- APEC) strains in the world.

Keywords: Page therapy; Bacteriophages; Avian pathogenic *Escherichia coli*; Multidrug resistance; coliphages.

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Étude comparative de la présence des résidus des substances à activité antimicrobiennes dans les foies des volailles consommée dans la région de Souk- Ahras

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Résumé :

Les antibiotiques utilisés en aviculture sont susceptibles de se retrouver dans les denrées alimentaires d'origine animale et constituent un risque pour la santé publique. Cette étude a pour but la recherche des résidus d'antimicrobien dans les foies des volailles.

Au total 82 échantillons (dont 50 foies du poulet et 32 foies de dinde) ont été collectés au hasard à partir de différents boucheries et fermes au niveau de la wilaya de Souk Ahras puis analysés par la méthode microbiologique de diffusion en gélose utilisant trois souches bactériennes sensibles à savoir : *Staphylococcus aureus* ATCC 23, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* ATCC 53 et *Escherichia coli* ATCC 22.

L'étude a montré que sur les 82 échantillons des foies analysés, 54 foies sont contaminés par des résidus d'antibiotiques, avec un taux de contamination global de 65,85%.

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Pour le poulet de chair, les résultats ont montré que 90% contenant des quinolones (enrofloxacin), 58% des tétracyclines, 88% des macrolides (érythromycine) et 33% d'antibiotiques polypeptidiques (colistine).

En ce qui concerne le foie de dinde de chair, les résultats ont montré que 28,13% contenant des macrolides (érythromycine), 25% des quinolones (enrofloxacin), 12,5% d'antibiotique polypeptidique (colistine) et 6,25% des tétracyclines.

Ces résultats montrent que le taux de contamination est plus élevé pour les foies de poulet que pour les foies de dinde.

Mots clé : résidus d'antibiotiques, foie de poulet, foie de dinde, méthode microbiologique, souk ahras.

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**STUDY OF THE PREVALENCE OF DIFFERENT SEROTYPES OF SALMONELLA
AND THEIR PROFILES OF SENSITIVITY AND RESISTANCE TO ANTIBIOTICS
IN POULTRY FARMS IN THE EASTERN REGION OF ALGERIA.**

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Abstract

The aim of this study was to provide information on the degree of contamination by salmonella and the prevalence of its serotypes as well as their susceptibility profile to different antibiotics in poultry farms in the eastern region of Algeria.

This study was conducted in 114 poultry farms (47 broilers ; 43 laying hens; 10 turkey ; 12 broilers breeders; 02 layers breeders) in the province of Sétif, BordjBouArerridj, Msila, Batna, Constantine, Mila, Skikda, Oum El Bouaghi, (East of Algeria). Biological samples (organs: livers, hearts, ovaries, yolks) were taken from suspect farms (based on clinical signs and necropsy at autopsy) , then the samples were sent to the laboratory for the various microbiological examinations (isolation, identification, serotyping,and antibiogram).

Almost 37.72% of poultry farms were contaminated with Salmonella . The isolated Salmonella strains were four main serotypes: S.Enteritidis (44.19%), S.Gallinarum (46.51%), S.Pullorum (6.98%), and S.O6.7(2.32%).

The following percentages were found for the results of the antibiograms carried out on all the isolated strains: 82.86% of the strains were sensitive to ampicillin while 99.94% were sensitive to amoxicillin combined with clavulanic acid; 100% of strains were susceptible to Cefotaxim, gentamycin, colistin, enrofloxacin, and chloramphenicol , 74.29% of strains were sensitive to tetracyclines, 85.71% of strains were susceptible to trimethoprim associated with

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sulfamithoxazol, 42.86% of the strains susceptible to nitrofurans , but 100% of the isolated strains were resistant to nalidixic acid.

Salmonella remains a concern due to its contamination of poultry farms either by nonparatyphoid serotypes (S.Gallinarum-pullorum) which are specific to poultry or by paratyphoid serotypes (S.Typhimerium;S. Enteritidis) that cause zoonoses.

Our study showed a significant presence of paratyphoid serotypes of Salmonella in poultry production on the Eastern region of Algeria, This requires that periodic control and biosecurity measures be strictly applied to safeguard the public health of consumers.

These results showed variable antibiotic sensitivity and resistance profiles, so a well-considered use of antibiotics will prevent the emergence of strains with resistance factors.

Keywords: Salmonella , serotype, prevalence, breeding, poultry.

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Hygiène à la traite et impact sur la qualité du lait et la santé de la mamelle

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Résumé

Les mammites constituent une entrave à l'essor de la production laitière. Ces affections multifactorielles représentent un trouble majeur chez la vache laitière, située au carrefour de la qualité du lait et de la santé mammaire. La gestion des mammites est un vrai enjeu pour l'économie d'élevage.

L'étude a permis de mettre en évidence une carence des règles d'hygiène de la traite souvent encore non maîtrisée au niveau des élevages bovins laitiers. Afin d'améliorer la qualité du lait cru, différentes mesures préconisées dans les étables lors de la traite doivent être appliquées plus rigoureusement par les éleveurs. Ces mesures ont une double action, elles permettent non seulement de réduire la contamination du lait par les micro-organismes de l'environnement, mais également de diminuer les risques de pénétration des germes des trayons dans la mamelle.

Mots-clés : Hygiène -Traite- Qualité du lait -Santé mammaire

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Mycobacteria Strains Isolated from Fish: Ecological and Health Insights

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Mycobacteria comprise a diverse group that includes pathogenic as well as nonpathogenic, yet sometimes opportunistic, species posing significant risks to human and animal public health, and aquatic ecosystems due to the severity of the diseases they cause. Our study aimed primarily to isolate and identify strains of mycobacteria present in various fish species.

At the Laboratory of Microbial Ecology, University of Bejaia, we analyzed a total of 507 organ samples from fish using bacteriological methods. Each sample underwent decontamination to remove external and internal contaminants. Subsequently, samples were cultured on Lowenstein Jensen medium and placed in an incubator at 30°C for 8 weeks. Identification of mycobacterial isolates was conducted by closely observing the morphological characteristics of colonies formed on the culture medium. These characteristics include color, size, shape, and texture of colonies, which are important criteria for differentiating between different species of mycobacteria, supplemented by biochemical tests.

The results revealed the isolation of 55 strains of mycobacteria from examined fish tissues. These findings clearly underscore the presence of these pathogens in fish, highlighting the potential risks they may pose to human and animal health, as well as the integrity of aquatic ecosystems.

Keywords: Mycobacteria, fish, public health, Bejaia

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BACTERIOLOGICAL QUALITY OF RAW MILK SOLD IN SOUK AHRAS REGION (ALGERIA)

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Abstract

Souk-Ahras region is considered as a dairy area, with a considerable cattle population and an annual milk production of 89,257.00L, it also benefits from a national rehabilitation program; But this foodstuff faces problems of deterioration in physico-chemical and microbiological quality. Our study aims at determining the quality of milk sold in Souk Ahras region, using bacteriological analyses dictated by national standards. Sixty samples of raw milk collected from six sales outlets and one collection center, were subjected to bacteriological tests in order to determine their bacteriological quality. The tests covered; Total aerobic mesophilic flora, faecal *coliforms*, faecal *Streptococci*, *Staphylococcus aureus* and sulfite-reducing *Clostridium*. Results show that 100% of samples were of unsatisfactory bacteriological quality. The number of samples with contamination levels exceeding the criteria for two different parameters was 76.67%, and 10% for three different parameters. Exceedances are due firstly to the presence of faecal *Streptococci* and secondly to *Staphylococcus aureus* (100% and 81.67%), with average counts of (9.7×10^2 and 31 mo ml^{-1}) respectively. These results reveal the risk of food poisoning associated with the consumption of raw milk, underlining the need to apply rigorous control throughout the dairy chain, respect the cold chain and introduce heat treatment for better preservation of this product.

Keywords: Raw milk; Bacteriological quality; food poisoning; Souk-Ahras

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Can food of animal origin pose a microbiological hazard in Souk Ahras ?

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Abstract

Foods of animal origin such as milk and meat have a high nutritional value and form an important part of the human and animal diet, but are difficult to produce and are highly perishable. If, however, production and/or storage conditions are neglected, the result will be significant socio-economic loss, whether through loss of the food or illnesses caused by consumption and treatment. It was in this context that we carried out this study, to assess the hygienic quality of cow's milk and meat produced and consumed in a border region of Algeria.

A total of 130 samples were taken from animal foodstuffs (raw cow's milk, sheep carcasses, chicken and turkey meat) at farm, abattoir and butchery levels. Mesophilic aerobic flora, total coliforms, thermotolerant coliforms and *E. coli* were enumerated, and the sensitivity of the *E. coli* identified to certain antibiotics most commonly used in human and veterinary medicine was assessed.

High levels of contamination and bacterial loads ranging from 5.36×10^{-2} CFU.mL⁻¹ for milk, to 1.56×10^5 CFU.cm⁻² for sheep meat, some of our foodstuffs are acceptable but contain a food hazard, and others are not acceptable according to regulations. A high percentage of multiresistant strains and worrying resistance rates, and if the necessary measures are not taken as a matter of urgency in the context of "One Health", the situation is likely to worsen and human and animal health will be affected.

Keywords: food of animal origin, microbiological quality, *E. coli*, Antibiotic resistance, Algeria.

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Analyses physico-chimique et microbiologique du fromage fondu à L'Est Algérien

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Résumé

Les fromages fondus sont des aliments complexes habituellement obtenus en mélangeant une ou plusieurs variétés de fromages avec des agents émulsifiants (les sels de fonte), de nombreux ingrédients optionnels incluant des ingrédients laitiers et de l'eau.

Dans ce travail nous nous sommes intéressées au fromage fondu industriel et artisanal commercialisés à l'est algérien. Par l'analyse de certains paramètres physicochimique et microbiologique afin de contrôler la qualité du deux types de fromages.

Cette étude est basée sur le suivi de 2 analyses qui ont porté sur : Les analyses physicochimiques : pH, Acidité titrable, EST, Teneur en Matière Minérale, Teneur en Matière Organique, Taux d'humidité et le degré Brix. Les analyses microbiologiques : déterminations de la flore mésophile aérobie totale, les coliformes totaux et fécaux, les streptocoques totaux et fécaux, les staphylocoques pathogènes, *Salmonella*, *Clostridium* Sulfito-réducteurs, *Listeria monocytogene*, levures et moisissures.

Les résultats des analyses physico-chimiques obtenus, nous notons que le pH, l'acidité titrable du fromage fondu industriel et artisanal sont conformes aux normes, Tandis que l'EST, la teneur en matière minérale et matière organique sont inférieurs et/ou supérieurs aux normes pour le fromage artisanal ceci peut avoir une influence sur le goût, la texture... du fromage.

De point de vue microbiologique les résultats ont montrés que la flore mésophile aérobie totale est présente avec une charge qui ne dépasse pas la norme pour le fromage industriel, et qu'elle dépasse la norme pour le fromage artisanal. L'absence totale des coliformes et des streptocoques totaux et fécaux, des salmonelles, des staphylocoques dans le fromage industriel avec des charges très élevées pour le fromage artisanal. Les levures et moisissures sont présentes avec une charge qui ne dépasse pas la norme pour le fromage industriel avec une charge élevée pour le fromage artisanal.

Mot clé : fromage fondu ; fromage industriel ; microbiologique ; physico-chimiques ; fromage artisanal

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A Comparative Histological study of Testicles and Epididymis in Domestic Animals (Dogs and Cats) versus Wild Animals (Genets and Mongooses)

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Abstract

Testicular cryopreservation is crucial for maintaining reproductive functions and creating germplasm banks for commercially significant species or those at risk of extinction. This study seeks to offer additional insights into the morphological and histological characteristics of the testes across various selected species, compare the testes of two predatory animals (mongoose and genet) with those of two domestic animals (cat and dog). The research involves direct observation, the preparation of histological sections, and precise measurements of the diameters of seminiferous tubules and epididymal ducts. To this end, the testes and epididymides were excised and promptly fixed. Histological comparisons revealed that dogs have notably larger testicular sizes compared to the other species, with significant differences observed between wild and domestic animals. Further research is necessary to explore the substantial differences resulting from selective breeding and to consider the use of biotechnologies, such as artificial insemination, to enhance the reproduction of species, particularly those at risk of extinction.

Key -words: Pets-epididymal-canals; Histology; Testis; Wild-animals; Algeria.

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Stress to slaughter and quality of meat in broiler

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Abstract

Slaughter is mean stressor factor for livestock animals. It affects negatively the organoleptic and health qualities of the meat. Our study was carried out in classic, semi-traditional slaughterhouses in eastern Algeria. It had assessed the response to the slaughter stress of three lots of broilers of ISA strain with fast growing trait and different weights.

The physiological parameters (body temperature, heart rate and respiratory rate) were measured in pre-slaughter stage, in farms before delivery of broiler chicken then at their arrival to slaughterhouses. In post-slaughter, investigations on meat are carried out at different times (2h-12h and 24h) : pH of breast fillets and thighs, exudates losses, cooking yield and the sensory analysis of the color on the sixth day.

The results of physiological parameters of broilers showed stressful conditions of transport and unloading. Hyperthermia ($42.55^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 0.28$), bradycardia ($28.78\text{bpm} \pm 1.96$) and respiratory rate ($24.89\text{mvt} / \text{min} \pm 2.75$) confirm the established constitution. These parameters are significantly correlated with muscle acidity ($p < 0.01$). In post-slaughter the ultimate thighs pH at 24h PM; are significantly higher ($p < 0.05$) than those of breast fillets (6.19 ± 0.09 vs. 6.11 ± 0.10), leading to high losses by spontaneous discharge ($11\% \pm 1.45$ and $6\% \pm 2.80$), and by cooking yield ($78\% \pm 0.06$ vs. $90\% \pm 0.06$) of breast fillets and thighs, respectively. Individual variability (intra-batch) at all measurement times and for the two muscles; indicates a genetic influence on the response to slaughter stress ($P < 0.001$).

Exudates losses are negatively correlated with pHu ($r = -0.75$ and -0.69 , $p < 0.001$), and with technological efficiency ($r = -0.90$ and -0.84 , $p < 0.001$). Furthermore, significant effect of the live weight of slaughtered chickens on pHu was established, especially of the thigh ($r = -0.59$; $p < 0.05$). Generally; the sensory analysis of the color confirmed that slaughter stress affects broiler carcasses; leading to the expected effects (Dark, Firm and Dry meat).

Key Words: Algeria- Broiler – Quality -Meat- Slaughter -Stress.

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Effect of Prickly Pear Extracts (*Opuntia Ficus-indica*) on the Growth of Rabbits *ORYCTOLAGUS Cuniculus*

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Abstract

Due to multiple uses of *Opuntia Ficus Indica*, we dedicated a quantitative study following a biological analysis on seeds, or this species was collected on Out 2021 from the area of Sidi-Fredj wilaya of Souk-Ahras (North-East Algeria). In the present study, the chemical analysis of the seeds powder of barbaric fig seeds reveals a moisture percentage of 92% of the dry matter. A yield of 4.36 ± 0.57 and 5.76 ± 0.55 for hydromethanol extract and ethyl acetate respectively. Phytochemical screening reveals the presence of certain secondary metabolites such as tannins, flavonoids, alkaloids, amines, polyphenols and steroids, and the absence of others such as reducing sugars and quinones, in the different types of extracts.

The quantitative analysis was carried out on four types of organic extracts; Methanol, Ethyl Acetate, Ethanol and Hexane, passed by the dosage of Tanins, Flavonoids, and Total Polyphenols. The results obtained from quantitative analyses show that the methanoic extract still has higher values for the three dosages, ($316 \mu\text{g/ml} \pm 14,42$; $182,51 \mu\text{g/ml} \pm 2,18$; $454,33 \mu\text{g/mL} \pm 2,08$ respectively), following the ethyl acetate ($283,38 \mu\text{g/mL} \pm 1,19$; $118,33 \mu\text{g/mL} \pm 1,52$; $409,4 \mu\text{g/mL} \pm 0,52$ respectively). Antioxidant power in vitro was estimated by total antioxidant activity, it shows that ethyl acetate and methanol have moderate activity by intake of hexan and ethanol ($3.91 \mu\text{g/ml} \pm 0.74$; $3.56 \mu\text{g/mL} \pm 1.15$; $3.27 \mu\text{g/mL} \pm 0.11$; $3.01 \mu\text{g/mL} \pm 1.02$ respectively), the FRAP iron reduction test has an CI50 of $22.09 \mu\text{g/mm} \pm 2.73$ in methanole as

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the most active extract, that of Ascorbic acid $1.21\mu\text{g}/\text{mg}\pm 0.36$ as positive test indicators. For the 2,2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl radical reduction test the ethanol extract has an CI_{50} of $2.19\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}\pm 1.16$ as the next highest value of Ethyl Acetate with an IC_{50} of $1.93\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}\pm 0.54$. With regard to the beta-carotene bleaching test the important anti-radical activity is observed in methanol following ethyl acetate (%AA = $2.04\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}\pm 0.46$; $1.82\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}\pm 0.33$ respectively). On the other hand, the *in vivo* study on rabbits *Oryctolagus Cuniculus* treated with the feed from seed 'the turtles', shows a better evolution of the rabbit weight under feeding for the improvement of weight gain, nutritional efficiency and carcass yield in rabbits at the age of 71 days. Best dietary and organoleptic quality of rabbit meat species. Biochemical analyses show disturbances in some parameters and decreases in others.

It is concluded that the fig tree is a highly sought after plant in various industries, and in the feeding of cattle. Further studies on its nutritional effectiveness and how it is used in animal feeding are recommended for better valorisation of this plant.

Keywords: *Opuntia – Ficus-Indica*; seeds; *in vitro* biological analysis; *in vivo* studies.

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Impact of intensification on milk parameters in the southeast of Algeria

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Abstract:

Many countries, including Algeria, have implemented intensive camel breeding systems to boost productivity. This study aimed to evaluate the effect of intensification on camel milk yield and its compositional parameters. A total of 100 camel milk samples were analyzed using a Lactoscan milk analyzer (Lactoscan® SAP50). Fifty samples were collected from camels raised under intensive systems, while the other fifty came from camels raised under extensive systems, all from El Oued province in southeastern Algeria. The impact of these breeding systems was analyzed using ANOVA. The results indicated that camels raised under extensive systems produced milk with significantly higher fat content ($P=0.001$). In contrast, camels in intensive systems produced milk with significantly higher solid non-fat (SNF) content ($P=0.000$), density ($P=0.000$), lactose ($P=0.001$), and salt content ($P=0.036$), as well as a greater overall milk yield ($P=0.016$). These findings suggest that intensive camel breeding significantly influences both milk yield and composition, potentially offering advantages in terms of milk quality and quantity, depending on the intended use.

Keys words: Camel, milk, intensive, extensive, Algeria

DAY 2

PLANT BIOTECHNOLOGY

ORAL COMMUNICATIONS

IN VITRO* STUDY OF ANTIOXIDANT AND ANTI INFLAMMATORY PROPERTIES OF ORGANIC EXTRACTS FROM *VINICA DIFFORMIS

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Abstract

Vinica Difformis (Apocynaceae) has been used since ancient times in traditional medicine to treat many diseases. It was used as a gargle against tonsillitis and externally on wounds, bruises, hemorrhoids, and bleeding gums. This study was designed to evaluate the antioxidant and anti-inflammatory activities of organic extracts of the leaves, the flowers and the stems of *Vinica Difformis*. The total phenolic and flavonoid contents as well as the antioxidant and the anti-inflammatory effects of chloroform, ethyl acetate, and butanol extracts have been investigated by using different *in-vitro* methods. It was found that the ethyl acetate extract had the highest total phenolic content and a high concentration of flavonoids. It was also found that this extract exhibited the highest activity in scavenging of 2,2-diphenyl- 1-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH), as well as in ABTS test. On the other hand, this extract inhibited the denaturation of bovine serum albumin (BSA) caused by heat (72°C), which means it has anti-inflammatory activity. This study provides a scientific basis for the traditional use of *Vinica Difformis* as an anti-inflammatory agent and for the plant to be considered as an important resource of natural antioxidants.

Key words: *Vinica Difformis*, antioxidant activity, anti-inflammatory activity, total phenolic, flavonoid contents.

Biodegradable Emulsified Films based on Polysaccharides Blend and Microcrystalline Wax: Elaboration and Characterization

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Abstract: Films based on polysaccharides have generally weak barrier properties against water vapor, generally the water vapor fluxes are high compared to those of synthetic polymers and depends on several factors, in particular; structure and their hydrophilic nature, which limits their use. The properties of these films can be improved by the use of hydrophobic compounds. By combining polysaccharides and hydrophobic compounds, it is possible to develop a biodegradable packaging where each component will aid in improving the film functionality. The aim of the present work is the development and characterization of new formulation of emulsified films based on soluble starch/sodium alginate blend and microcrystalline wax. The developed films were studied in order to use them as new formulations to produce food packaging. The obtained films were generally homogeneous, thin, and slightly flexible. These films were appeared more opaque compared to the non-emulsified film. Incorporation of microcrystalline wax were caused modifications of mechanical properties of films, these modifications were principally due to the formation of amylose-lipid complex. It was found that microcrystalline significantly reduced film water vapor permeability (WVP) of emulsified films. Atomic force microscope (AFM) was used to evaluate surface topography and roughness of the films. The surface topography was significantly affected, in the other word high roughness values were obtained. Microemulsion formation in which the microcrystalline wax particles are distributed homogeneously within the polymer matrix was investigated by scanning electron microscopy (SEM). Moreover, the polysaccharides blend/microcrystalline wax emulsified films can be useful as a biodegradable packaging material to maintain the quality of food products.

Keywords : Polysaccharides blend, microcrystalline wax, Emulsified films, hydrophilic, hydrophobic.

Procédé d'extraction du charbon actif à partir des déchets agricole (grignons d'olives) et son utilisation comme fertilisant des sols sableux dans le milieu aride

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Résumé

Ce travail de recherche se concentre sur la valorisation des grignons d'olives en charbon actif pour améliorer la fertilité des sols sahariens en Algérie. Face aux défis de l'agriculture dans des conditions climatiques variées, notamment la sécheresse et la pauvreté des sols, cette étude propose une solution innovante et durable. En utilisant les ressources locales disponibles à Skikda, cette recherche a démontré la faisabilité de produire un fertilisant bio à partir de déchets agricoles, réduisant ainsi l'empreinte environnementale tout en augmentant la productivité agricole. Les résultats soulignent l'efficacité du charbon actif pour améliorer la rétention d'eau et la fertilité des sols sahariens, tout en ouvrant des perspectives pour une mise en œuvre industrielle à grande échelle. Ce projet s'inscrit dans une démarche de développement durable visant à renforcer la sécurité alimentaire et à promouvoir une agriculture plus résiliente aux changements climatiques en Algérie. La méthode consiste à récupérer des déchets des grignons d'olive souvent rejetés sauvagement dans la nature et les cours d'eau pour extraire le charbon actif au niveau du laboratoire en passant du lavage, au broyage, carbonisation à l'activation chimique. Les résultats sont très satisfaisants dans la mesure où le charbon actif extrait au laboratoire a été testé sur un certain nombre de substrat (sol) de texture différente et de culture différent (maraichage), ce qui a donné des résultats extraordinaire. Grâce à ses caractéristiques spécifiques, le charbon actif aura deux rôles essentiels à savoir : l'augmentation de la capacité d'adsorption du sol en eau et l'amélioration de l'adsorption des cultures. L'extrait obtenu dans le laboratoire a été utilisé à petite échelle sur de nombreuses cultures maraichère avec des doses différentes, il pourrait être efficacement utilisé comme additif avec les engrais minéraux. Cette invention pourrait révolutionner l'agriculture dans les régions saharienne et les terres touchées par la sécheresse dans la Nord du pays

Keywords: Grignons d'olives, Oléiculture, Déchets agricoles, Charbon actif, Agriculture saharienne

Advancements in Cherry Genetics: Unraveling Key Genes and Genomic Tools for Enhancing Agronomic Traits

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Abstract:

Cherry trees play a vital role in global fruit production, offering significant economic and nutritional benefits. Enhancing key agronomic traits such as fruit size, quality, and disease resistance is crucial for optimizing cherry cultivation. This study examines recent advances in understanding the genetic basis of these traits through a comprehensive review of scientific literatures and analysis of recent research papers on cherry genetics. Key findings include the identification of important genes related to fruit size, flavor, and texture, such as *SQUAMOSA PROMOTER BINDING PROTEIN-LIKE* (SPL) and *MADS-box* transcription factors, as well as genes associated with disease resistance, including members of the *NBS-LRR* gene family. The reviews highlight advancements in genomic tools, including genomic selection and CRISPR/Cas9 gene editing, which have improved trait identification and precision breeding. Trait mapping studies have pinpointed specific genomic regions linked to agronomic traits, and functional genomics research has provided insights into the roles of *ethylene-responsive factors* in fruit ripening. Despite these advancements, challenges such as the complexity of polygenic traits and the need for integrated omics approaches remain. Future research should focus on validating these findings through field trials and integrating multi-omics data for a comprehensive understanding of cherry genetics. Recent advancements offer promising opportunities for improving cherry tree breeding programs and cultivation practices, with a focus on addressing trait complexity and leveraging integrated approaches for future progress.

Key words: cherry genetics, agronomic traits, genomic tools, trait mapping, precision breeding

Evaluation of Glycerin-Citric Acid-Based NADES for Efficient Green Extraction of Bioactive Compounds

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Abstract

Natural DeepEutecticSolvents(NADES) have emerged as newlyadopted, eco-friendly alternatives for extracting bioactive compounds, providing a non-toxic and sustainable solution compared to traditionalorganicsolvents. This studyprimarilyaims to identify the most effective NADES for extracting bioactive compounds and to compare itwithaconventional solvent. Various NADES werepreparedusingspecificsugars and organicacids, combinedwithglycerin. In the extraction process, 1g of powderfroma fruit of algerianspontaneoustreewas mixed with 20ml of each NADES, followed by agitation and heating for 1 hour. The resultsclearlydemonstratethat the NADES composed of citricacid and glycerinyielded the highest extraction efficiency, with a total polyphenol content of 9.87 mg GAE/g of dry powder, flavonoid content of 3.41 mg CE/g of dry powder, and a DPPH radical scavengingactivity of 82.79%. Whencompared to the resultsobtainedwith 70% ethanol, whichyielded a total polyphenol content of 6.09 mg GAE/g, a flavonoid content of 1.82 mg CE/g, and antioxidantactivity of 87.89%, the glycerin-citricacid-based NADES proved to behighly effective. Thesefindingsvalidatethatthisparticular NADES iseffective andoffers a non-toxic alternative for variouspotential applications.

Keywords: NADES, Bioactive Compounds, Extraction, Polyphenols.

Exopolysaccharides of Extremophilic Bacteria: Effective Agents for Applications in the Food Industry

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Abstract

Exopolysaccharides (EPS) are one of biopolymers produced by bacterial communities to survive various extreme environmental conditions. EPS are extracellular carbohydrate biopolymers produced and secreted by microorganisms, which accumulate outside cells, they are able to be released into the surrounding environment. EPS produced by extremophiles have attracted potential research interest for several biotechnological applications due to their good thermal stability, non-toxicity and biodegradability.

For example, food industries around the world are looking for value-added compounds or additives of natural origin with increased functionality and bioactivity. This communication aims to give an overview about the potential applications of bacterial EPS.

Isolation of bacterial strains was carried out by plating the serially diluted water samples on nutrient agar followed by incubation for 24 to 48 h, then screened for EPS production based on slimy appearance of their colonies. The selected colonies were inoculated in a nutrient broth for EPS quantification. The functional properties of EPS were evaluated for food industry applications.

EPS play an important role in improving the rheological and sensory characteristics of food products by positively influencing food texture and organoleptic properties. Moreover, these biomolecules have been considered as promising antioxidants for developing effective functional foods with longer shelf life.

In conclusion, we can deduce that EPS are promising candidates that can be useful additives for the food industry. Thus, the production and characterization of extremophilic bacterial EPS is an active area of research to improve culture techniques, in a cost-effective manner.

Keywords: Exopolysaccharides ; Biopolymers ; Extremophiles ; Food Industries.

***In Vitro* Antioxidant, Phenolic and Flavonoid Contents of Different Polarity Extracts of an algerian medicinal plant from southern Algeria of (Fabaceae) Aerial Parts**

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Abstract

For the valorization of medicinal wild herbs growing in the Algerian Sahara, we conducted a phytochemical study and estimated the antioxidant capacity of the Fabaceae. It is also distinguished by its wide therapeutic uses. Antioxidants play an important role of protecting the human body against damage by the free radicals. Plants containing phenolic compounds have been reported to possess strong antioxidant properties. Hence, this study focuses on the evaluation of the antioxidant activity, total phenolic and flavonoid contents of different polarity extracts of an algerian medicinal plant from southern Algeria of (Fabaceae) Aerial Parts.

Our work is dedicated to a phytochemical and biological study of chloroform, ethyl acetate and *n*-butanol extracts from the aerial parts (leaves and flowers) of a species belonging of the Fabaceae family. The objective of our study concerns the following investigations:

- A phytochemical screening aimed at characterizing the different classes of secondary metabolites by precipitation and coloring reactions.
- Thin layer chromatography (TLC on silica gel)
- The quantification of the levels of flavonoids (TFC), and polyphenols (TPC) by the necessary colorimetric methods (Folin- Ciocalteu was used for the quantification of TPC and the method of aluminum chloride AlCl₃ was employed for the TFC).

- The *in vitro* biological evaluation was carried out on the extracts, focusing on the study of the properties: antioxidant (four ways antioxidants: DPPH, ABTS, FRAP and PHENANTHROLINE).

Phytochemical screening has shown that our extracts contain various types of secondary metabolites and in varying amounts such as: Flavonoids, terpenoids, tannins, alkaloids, saponosids, anthraquinons and coumarins.

The ethyl acetate extract exhibited the best antioxidant activity in all tests and also showed the highest amount of total phenelic content and flavonoid content.

Fabaceae family extract exhibited antioxidant properties and could serve as primary antioxidants for pharmaceutical plant-based products.

Key words: Fabaceae, TPC, TFC, antioxidant, FRAP.

Influence of other heavy metals on nickel adsorption onto activated carbon prepared from chestnut shell

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Abstract

Despite advancements in technology and enhanced regulation, the pollution generated by numerous industrial processes continues to rise, resulting in the deterioration of water resources. Industrial effluents that contain heavy metals such as nickel, copper, lead, cadmium, and zinc are harmful to human health. Over the past three decades, extensive research has been conducted to elucidate the adsorption of heavy metals in aqueous solutions. However, the majority of studies have concentrated on the adsorption of individual metal ions in aqueous solutions. However, wastewater most often contains more than one type of metal ions. Based on the composition of the species coexisting in the associated effluents, various scenarios can be contemplated i) a synergetic effect; where species adsorption is emphasized, ii) a hindrance effect; where, the adsorption of a kind of heavy metal ions is inhibited or iii) a global slowdown is observed leading to a diminution of all the species adsorption. In this study, the adsorption of nickel ions was examined both in single and multi-metal configuration where copper and chromium ions were concurrently considered with nickel ions. The activated carbon prepared from chestnut shell was used as the adsorbent. The obtained results showed that the inclusion of copper and chromium in the synthetic solution leads to a significant decrease in the adsorption of nickel ions compared to a single metal configuration.

Keywords: Adsorption; Heavy Metals; Activated Carbon; Water Treatment; Competition.

Innovation and food safety: biodegradable packaging, a solution for the future

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Abstract

The escalating environmental crisis, largely driven by the ubiquitous use of synthetic polymers in packaging, has spurred a concerted effort within the food and packaging industries to explore sustainable alternatives. For decades, plastics have been the material of choice for preserving food due to their exceptional properties. However, their detrimental impact on the environment, coupled with the dwindling fossil fuel reserves, has necessitated a shift towards renewable resources. Biodegradable films, derived from natural sources, offer a promising avenue for developing packaging solutions that can effectively protect food while minimizing ecological harm. By acting as barriers to moisture, oxygen, lipids, and flavors, these films can extend product shelf life and reduce food waste. This study aims to design and characterize functional biomaterials derived from by-product waste to extend food shelf life, mitigate plastic pollution, and promote circular economy principles by developing biodegradable, compostable materials. starch and coffee grounds waste in the proportions of 100:0, 90:10, 80:20, 70:30, and 60:40% (w/w) were used. Physical, mechanical, barrier and antioxidant properties of the developed films were evaluated. The addition of coffee grounds enhanced the mechanical strength of the films while reducing their water solubility and water vapour permeability, thus improving their overall properties. Les résultats ont montré une diminution spectaculaire du poids des films entant qu'indicateur de biodégradabilité. La perte de poids pourrait être due à deux raisons : l'action de désintégration par la microflore présente dans le sol, et la solubilisation des composants du film par l'ajout d'eau dans le sol. En conséquence, les films ont été presque désintégrés et leurs formes d'origine ont été totalement perdues. Cependant, aucune différence significative dans les valeurs de biodégradabilité n'a été observée entre les films. These results demonstrate the potential of bio composites to replace conventional plastics and promote a circulareconomy for better conservation of agricultural produce.

Keywords: pollution, biomaterials, biodegradable, packaging, plastic.

Morphological and molecular characterization of some Algerian male date palm: Identification of “*Deglet-Nour*” pollinator

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Abstract

In Algeria, the date palm (*Phoenix dactylifera* L.) is considered a strategic plant. Studying its genetic diversity, both male and female plants is an essential step in setting up breeding and improvement programs. For this work, in addition to studying the genetic diversity of male plants (dokkars), our investigation aims to identify the pollinators genetically closest to the female genotype “*Deglet-Nour*”; the important commercial cultivar. Several types of dokkars, and several female accessions assigned to the “*Deglet-Nour*” cultivar or others, from the Zibans region, were characterized using morphological descriptors (*IPGRI*, *MOCAF*, and other traits) and molecular SSR loci (25 SSR).

Our results revealed a high genetic variability over the 50 samples studied. The morphological and molecular characterization suggests that the “*Deglet-Nour*” accessions seem to have a homogeneous genetic basis compared to the other accessions, more deeply, the molecular results indicate the presence of a potential SSR marker specific to male and female individuals of this cultivar, so that it could be used as a potential marker for its selecting, at early stage of the plant. The majority of accessions of dokkar “*Deglet-Nour*” seem to be the closest to the female cultivar “*Deglet-Nour*”, in terms of the vegetative and molecular part, compared to the other accessions studied (dokkars / cultivars), This could be used as a means of certification and control of Algerian “*Deglet-Nour*” products.

Keywords: date palm, genetic diversity, dokkars, morphological descriptors, molecular markers.

**Phytochemical Elucidation and Antioxidant Activity of *Opuntia ficus-indica* seeds oil
from Tebessa Region, Algeria.**

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Abstract

Opuntia ficus-indica is a Cactaceae plant which has been used for centuries as dietary resources and in traditional folk medicine for its nutritional and healthy properties. This research aimed to enhance the value of cactus seeds to place a spotlight on the chemical profile and antioxidant activity of prickly pear. Phytochemical assays were employed to determine the chemical composition of prickly pear seed oil, which was subsequently characterized using Gas Chromatography-Tandem Mass Spectrometry for an in-depth analysis of their fatty acid composition. The in vitro antioxidant activity was evaluated using DPPH and FRAP methods. As indicated by GC-MS analyses, which allowed for the qualitative and quantitative identification of twenty-two fatty acids; Four major fatty acids were detected with high concentrations, Methyl Linoleate (C18:2) emerged as the dominant compound with a concentration of 227817.350 µg/µL, followed by Methyl cis-9 Oleate (C18:1) with a concentration of 44217.976 µg/µL, Methyl Palmitate (C16:0) with a concentration of 36517.951 µg/µL, and Methyl Stearate (C18:0) with a concentration of 11866.993 µg/µL. The evaluation of antioxidant was found that the *Opuntia ficus-indica* seeds oil has an important ability to transform ferric iron into ferrous iron with A_{0.5} value of 0.123 mg/mL and it has an antioxidant activity, causing the reduction of DPPH • radical to its non-radical form DPPH-H; with an IC₅₀ inhibitory concentration value of 0.050 mg/mL. The data provided through this study is crucial for the valorisation of *Opuntia ficus indica* seeds as a natural antioxidant additive in the food industry.

Keywords: *Opuntia ficus indica*; seeds oil; GC-MS/MS analysis; DPPH; FRAP

Evaluating the Role of PGPR Strains in Boosting the Nutritional Quality of *Trifolium alexandrinum*

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Abstract

Trifolium alexandrinum, also known as berseem, is a key forage crop with significant value in animal feeding due to its high nutritional content. Enhancing the nutritional profile of this crop can improve livestock productivity and overall farm efficiency. Recent interest in Plant Growth-Promoting Rhizobacteria (PGPR) suggests they may offer a sustainable, eco-friendly approach to boosting plant growth, nutrient content, and stress resistance. This study evaluated the effectiveness of two specific PGPR strains, BT1 and BT2, in enhancing the nutritional attributes of *Trifolium alexandrinum* grown under natural field conditions. An open field experiment was conducted, applying 20 ml of each PGPR strain to separate treatment groups, with an untreated control group for comparison. The experiment was replicated five times to ensure reliable results. Nutritional parameters, including crude protein, crude fiber, and mineral content, were assessed at the flowering stage using Near-Infrared (NIR) spectroscopy. The results revealed that PGPR treatments significantly improved the nutritional quality of *Trifolium alexandrinum*. The crude protein content increased with both PGPR strains, with BT1 achieving a slightly higher level (17.27%) compared to BT2 (17.22%), and the control group showing the lowest content (16.05%). Crude fiber content was slightly higher in the BT1 group (26.81%) compared to BT2 (26.52%) and the control (26.13%), indicating enhanced plant robustness. The ash content, reflecting mineral composition, was highest in the BT1 group (11.54%), followed by the control (11.23%) and the BT2 group (11.04%). These findings suggest that PGPR, especially BT1, can significantly enhance the nutritive value of *Trifolium alexandrinum*, presenting a promising method for improving forage quality and supporting livestock productivity. Further research is needed to explore the broader applications of PGPR in different crops and environments to maximize agricultural benefits.

Key words: *Trifolium alexandrinum*; Plant Growth-Promoting Rhizobacteria (PGPR)

Nutritional quality; Forage enhancement

POSTER COMMUNICATIONS

Activité antioxydante des extraits phénoliques des parties aériennes de *Laurus nobilis* L.

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Résumé

Les composés bioactifs de plantes médicinales comme agents thérapeutiques sont responsables de leurs activités thérapeutiques telles que les activités antioxydantes. De ce fait, nous nous sommes intéressés à ce travail à la recherche des extraits phénoliques a pouvoir antioxydant d'une plante médicinale locale: *Laurus nobilis* L. connue sous le nom de Laurier.

L'extraction des composés phénoliques des différentes partiesaériennes (feuilles, fleurs et branches) de la plante a été effectuée par une macération dans un mélange hydroalcoolique. La teneur en phénols totaux, analysée par le réactif de Folin-Ciocalteu, variait de $5,35 \pm 0,03$ à $15,42 \pm 0,11$ mg EAG/g MS. Les concentrations totales de flavonoïdes, détectées à l'aide de chlorure d'aluminium, varient de $0,5 \pm 0,04$ à $2,78 \pm 0,05$ mg EQ/g MS.

L'Activité antioxydante des nos extraits est testée par trois tests: ABTS, DPPH et le Phosphomolybdate en utilisant l'acide ascorbique comme référence. Les résultats obtenus ont montré que nos extraits manifestent une forte activité antioxydante notamment l'extrait phénoliques des fleurs. Ce travail devra être confirmé par d'autres expériences afin d'identifier les molécules responsables à l'activité antioxydante et d'étudier leurs effets *in vivo*, utilisables ensuite en thérapeutique.

Mots-clés: Activité antioxydante, composés phénoliques, *Laurus nobilis* L.

Comparative analysis of organic extracts bioactivity from two *Limonium*.

Mill species growing wild in Tunisian salty marshes

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Abstract

Limonium. Mill is a genus of flowering plants belonging to the Plumbaginaceae family. The present study aimed to compare two *Limonium* species (*L. pruinosum* Kuntze and *L. tunetanum* (Barratte & Bonnet) Maire) in terms of their chemical composition and bioactivity. Chemical profiling showed that the methanolic (MeOH) extracts of both species were the most enriched with total phenolic (TP) and total flavonoid (TF) contents. The TFC were higher in *L. tunetanum* compared to *L. pruinosum*. HPLC-DAD analysis showed that distinctly the gallic acid and L-tyrosine 7-amido-4-methylcoumarin were the main compounds for *L. pruinosum* and *L. tunetanum*, respectively. For both *Limonium*. Mill species, the MeOH extracts displayed the highest antioxidant with IC₅₀ of 7.7 and 8.4 µg/mL for *L. pruinosum* and *L. tunetanum*, respectively. The highest anti-15-lipoxygenase activity was recorded in the ethyl acetate (IC₅₀ = 14.2 µg/mL) and methanol (IC₅₀ = 15.6 µg/mL) extracts for *L. pruinosum*. However, for *L. tunetanum* the best activity was recorded for dichloromethane extract (IC₅₀ = 10.4 µg/mL). *L. pruinosum* extracts displayed the highest cytotoxic activity against MCF-7 and HCT-116 cell lines compared to *L. tunetanum* ones. The obtained bioactivity discrepancy between *Limonium*. Mill species was discussed in relation to the organic extract chemical richness.

Keywords: *Limonium tunetanum*; *Limonium pruinosum*; Antioxidant; Chromatography; Bioactivity

Évaluation *in vitro* de l'effet antiurolithiasique de quelques extraits de *Cynodon dactylon*(L).Pers

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Résumé

Dans le but de traiter un problème de santé (la lithiase urinaire), de diminuer le facteur cristallogène et d'éviter la formation des calculs par précipitation de l'oxalate de calcium, nous avons entrepris l'étude *in vitro* sur l'inhibition de la cristallisation oxalocalcique et la dissolution des calculs rénaux en présence de différents extraits des parties aériennes et racines d'une plante médicinale saharienne de la région de Laghouat à savoir *Cynodon dactylon*(L). Pers.

Tout d'abord, une étude phytochimique et un dosage spectroscopique des composés phénoliques totaux de différents extraits de la plante a été effectuée. Les résultats obtenus ont montré que nos extraits sont riches en tanins catéchiqes, C-hétérosides et O-hétérosides à génines réduites, avec des teneurs en phénols totaux allant de $0,822 \pm 0,015$ jusqu'à $5,160 \pm 0,197$ mg EAG/g MS.

L'activité antiurolithiasique *in vitro* de divers extraits de plante a été réalisée par deux modèles différents : le modèle turbidimétrique et le modèle gravimétrique dans les deux tests, l'activité antiurolithiasique a été comparée à celle de deux inhibiteurs de référence: le citrate de sodium et le Succinimideparbiol. Les résultats obtenus, mesurés par les deux modèles, montrent clairement que l'extrait aqueux des racines de *Cynodon dactylon* (L). Pers a donné un pouvoir antiurolithique très important (> 50% d'inhibition) par rapport aux inhibiteurs standards.

Mots-clés: *Cynodon dactylon*(L). Pers, racines, activité antiurolithiasique, *in vitro*.

Elucidation of the biosynthetic pathways of bioactive compounds in halophilic actinomycetes

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Abstract:

Biodiversity, the variety of life on Earth, plays a crucial role in maintaining ecosystem balance and resilience. Extremophile actinomycetes, as a part of Earth's biodiversity, have evolved to thrive in harsh environments, are true factories for molecules. They produce a wide variety of bioactive compounds, some of which have antibiotic, antitumor, or immunomodulatory properties. Halophilic actinomycetes, these bacteria that thrive in salty environments, are particularly interesting for research due to their ability to produce unique molecules. Indeed, to survive in extreme conditions, these organisms have developed adaptation mechanisms that lead them to synthesize unique compounds. The exploration of biochemical processes in halophilic actinomycetes allows for the identification of new bioactive molecules and an understanding of the molecular mechanisms underlying their production. The study of halophilic actinomycetes offers numerous prospects for enhancing our understanding of biodiversity and for developing new applications in the field of health. By exploring the biochemical processes of these organisms, we can discover new molecules with interesting therapeutic properties and thus contribute to improving human health. The remarkable interest of actinomycetes with regard to its production of molecules with an important activity, push us to choose this taxon as our experiments, identifying halophile actinomycetes from diverse environments in Algeria and screening them for biocontrol activity studying. The properties of the produced biomolecules to understand their mode of action and target specificity and the biochemical tests, which clearly show the results highlighted various enzymatic activities, such as lipolytic, caseinolytic, cellulolytic, and coagulase The exploitation of extremophile actinomycetes in biological control represents a

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University of Gabes, Tunisia

promising approach to develop more sustainable and environmentally friendly crop protection solutions. However, further research is needed to better understand the mechanisms of action of these microorganisms and to develop effective and competitive commercial products.

Key words: biodiversity, health, halophilic actinomycetes, bioactive molecules, biochemical processes, drug discovery, biotechnologies.

Étude de l'activité antibactérienne de l'huile essentielle de *Mentha piperita* sur des bactéries de contamination alimentaire

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Abstract

La menthe poivrée, *Mentha piperita*, plante commune est, l'une des plantes les plus populaires en Algérie.

Elle appartient à la famille des *Lamiaceae*, et se présente sous forme herbacée. Les huiles essentielles de *Mentha piperita*, ont fait l'objet de plusieurs études qui ont montré qu'ils ont des propriétés antimicrobiennes, des activités antioxydante et anti-inflammatoire. Ils ont été employés en aromathérapie pour différentes propriétés et dans l'industrie pharmaceutique et thérapeutique. Dans ce travail, nous sommes intéressés à évaluer les spectres d'activité antimicrobienne de ces huiles essentielles *vis-à-vis* des bactéries de contamination alimentaire. L'hydrodistillation a été effectuée par un appareil de type Clevenger, 100 g de matière première a été traitée, la durée d'extraction est de l'ordre de 2 heures. L'activité antibactérienne a été étudiée *vis-à-vis* plusieurs souches bactériennes prélevés et identifiés à partir d'aliments ; à savoir la chair de poulet, la viande hachée en utilisant la méthode de diffusion de disque en milieu gélosé Mueller Hinton.

Les souches identifiées étaient *E.coli* et *Salmonella spp* .

L'activité antibactérienne de l'huile du *Mentha piperita* démontre un pouvoir antibactérien très important sur les souches isolées.

À l' lumière de nos résultats on peut dire les huiles essentielles pourraient servir comme conservateur alimentaire naturel pour améliorer la sécurité alimentaire et augmenter leur durée de conservation.

Mots clés: *Mentha piperita*, huile essentielle, activité antibactérienne, hydrodistillation.

Optimizing the Health Benefits of Green Table Olives production through Advanced Processing Techniques

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Abstract

Green table olives are highly valued for their health benefits but are rarely consumed in their natural state due to their pronounced bitterness. This bitterness necessitates various processing methods to make them suitable for direct human consumption. Table olives are the most widely favored fermented food in the Mediterranean region. The ripeness of the olives and the chosen processing method significantly influence the nutritional profile and sensory characteristics of table olives, which are notably recognized as a rich source of phenolic compounds. This study explores advanced processing techniques aimed at enhancing the health benefits of green table olives while reducing bitterness. Specifically, we investigate the use of ashes as a substitute for sodium hydroxide (NaOH) in the traditional Spanish-style debittering procedure. Ash, being a naturally occurring material, offers a more environmentally sustainable alternative that can reduce bitterness in olives and potentially improve their taste. To evaluate the effectiveness of ashes compared to the conventional NaOH procedure, we used Gordal and Sevilla olive varieties. The primary objective of this research was to determine the concentrations of carotenoids, flavonoids, polyphenols, and ortho-diphenols in the brine solutions at the conclusion of the spontaneous fermentation stage. The findings reveal that olives debittered with ashes had lower flavonoid concentrations and higher carotenoid activity compared to those debittered with NaOH for both the Gordal and Sevilla varieties. However, for polyphenols and ortho-diphenols, the olives debittered with ashes showed lower levels in the Sevilla variety. Conversely, the Gordal variety exhibited higher levels of polyphenols and ortho-diphenols when debittered with ashes.

Keywords: Table olives, Spanish style, ashes, polyphenols, orthodiphenols, carotenoids, debittered

La part de l'agriculture familiale dans l'économie ménagère

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Résumé :

L'agriculture en Algérie, constitue un secteur extrêmement important de l'économie nationale. Elle couvre une grande partie du territoire national et présente dans plus de 90% des 1541 communes existantes. Elle procure des emplois directs ou indirects à 13 millions d'algériens vivant en milieu rural leur permettant ainsi d'améliorer leurs conditions de vie et celles de leurs familles ; il est admis qu'un emploi dans la sphère production génère, au moins trois autres emplois (transport-commerce-valorisation...). L'agriculture familiale, dans la politique envisagée en matière d'agriculture et du développement rural, se caractérise par un lien privilégié entre l'activité économique, la structure familiale et le terroir. La main d'œuvre est composée principalement des membres de la famille qui ne sont pas salariés mais qui y trouvent un revenu

ainsi que l'agriculture familiale est un secteur clé qui contribue de manière significative à la prospérité du pays. Dans cet étude, nous explorerons l'importance de l'agriculture familiale en Algérie, en mettant l'accent sur sa contribution économique et ses avantages sociaux.

Mots clés :

Agriculture ; sécurité alimentaire ; environnement ; L'agriculture familiale ; ressources naturelle. l'économie ménagère

Landraces and wild *Brassica rapa* L. seeds: morphological characterization and germination

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Abstract

The *Brassica rapa* species has considerable economic importance in global agriculture and is characterized by a wide genetic diversity, resulting in a great phenotypic variation. Wild form (*B. rapa* subs. *sylvestris*) is widespread in north Algeria and turnip (*B. rapa* subsp. *rapa*), the most important morphotype in the species, is cultivated in Algeria as fodder crop or as vegetable. In this study, carried out as part of the H2020 PRIMA BrassExplor project, we used seeds from four wild and four cultivated accessions of *B. rapa*, collected in various regions of Algeria to their characterization on morphological and germination level under different climatic conditions. Morphological analyses of the seeds have highlighted considerable variability, in particular in the weight of the seeds. Analysis of the seminal integuments showed distinction between wild and cultivated seeds. Moreover, our results shown that the temperature, particularly cold, has an impact on the precocity and the speed of germination, but has no significant effect on the maximum germination rate. Our results provide useful indications for the improvement of the species, in particular in the prospects of its cultivation.

Keywords *Brassica rapa*; turnip landraces; wild form; seed traits; germination.

Morphometric Characterization of Some Cherry Varieties in Tlemcen

Region

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Abstract :

In Algeria, the cultivation of the sweet cherry tree *Prunus avium* dates back to the time of Roman colonization, over time it has become a well-established fruit crop with a significant socio-economic impact in some regions of Algeria, with a total annual production of 11,178 tons. Which makes the characterization and collection of information on this species essential for improvement and sustainable management. The study carried out in this work aims at a morphometric characterization to describe the phenotypic diversity of seventeen varieties of *Prunus avium* at the level of the wilaya of Tlemcen (9 stations), this description is based on 23 morphological markers (08 quantitative and 15 qualitative) cited in the UPOV descriptor. The statistical exploitation of the data collected showed us a significant polymorphism within the same variety and between varieties. Dur Noir variety had the greatest menstruation of fruit. Then we moved on to inferential analyses which showed the discrimination of quantitative and qualitative variables, in particular fruit-related traits. These results remain to be confirmed by the molecular tool.

Keywords: *Prunus avium*, sweet cherry, varieties, morphometric characterization, Tlemcen.

Novel Biogenic Synthesis of a Silver@Biochar of Punica Granatum L Nanocomposite as an Antimicrobial Agent and Photocatalyst for Methylene Blue Degradation

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Abstract

The conventional synthesis of nanomaterials employing physical and chemical methods usually requires high cost and toxic chemicals. Thus, a facile, ecofriendly, cost-effective, novel, and sustainable route for the synthesis of a silver-loaded biochar nanocomposite (Ag@biochar) using PunicaGranatumpeel , biomass is reported for the first time in this study to advocate many of the principles of green chemistry such as safer solvents and auxiliaries. UV spectroscopic analysis at 420 nm indicated the formation of silver nanoparticles (AgNPs). AgNPs on the surface of biochar were predominantly spherical with a size range of 25–35 nm and a surface area of 47.61 m² /g .Testing the photocatalytic potential of Ag@biochar to remove methylene blue from wastewater demonstrated its high removal efficiency that reached 88.4% due to its high efficiency of electron transfer confirmed via electrochemical impedance spectroscopy analysis and retained 70.65% after six cycles of reuse. Ag@biochar was shown to be a powerful broad-spectrum antimicrobial agent as it completely prevented the growth of Escherichia coli and also inhibited the growth of Pseudomonas aeruginosa, Bacillus subtilis, and Candida albicans with the inhibition zones of 19, 18, 22, and 16 mm, respectively.

Keywords : Biochar , Silver , Antimicrobial , Nanocomposites , Punica granatum L .

Optimisation des Processus de Production des Huiles d'Olive Extra-Vierge : Qualité et Techniques Innovantes

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Résumé

L'élaboration des huiles d'olive extra-vierge est un processus complexe qui requiert un savoir-faire minutieux à chaque étape. Tout commence par la récolte des olives, qui doit se faire à maturité optimale pour garantir la qualité de l'huile. Les olives sont ensuite triées et nettoyées pour éliminer les impuretés, suivi du broyage qui libère l'huile contenue dans les cellules des fruits. Le malaxage, effectué à température contrôlée, permet aux gouttes d'huile de se regrouper, facilitant leur extraction. Deux méthodes d'extraction, la pression à froid et la centrifugation, sont couramment utilisées, la seconde offrant une efficacité accrue. Après extraction, l'huile est décantée pour éliminer les résidus solides et l'eau, puis filtrée pour améliorer sa clarté. Un stockage adéquat est essentiel, l'huile devant être conservée dans des récipients hermétiques, à l'abri de la lumière et de la chaleur, afin de préserver ses propriétés organoleptiques. Les analyses organoleptiques des huiles produites révèlent des arômes riches et équilibrés, témoignant de l'efficacité du processus. Ce soin apporté à chaque étape est crucial pour obtenir une huile d'olive extra-vierge de haute qualité, répondant à la demande croissante des consommateurs pour des produits authentiques et sains. À l'avenir, des recherches pourraient explorer l'impact de différentes variétés d'olives et de techniques sur les caractéristiques finales de l'huile, visant à optimiser encore davantage la production.

Mots-clés : Huile d'olive extra-vierge, Production, Techniques, Qualité.

Predicting the impact of future climate change on the holm oak tree in

Algeria under the RCP2.6 -2070.

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Abstract

Climate change will affect forests in the future and will have a major impact on species adaption and dispersion. One of the primary species affecting Algerian forests that are being impacted by climate change is the holm oak tree (*Quercus ilex*). They play a particularly significant role in the social, economic, and environmental spheres.

The purpose of this study was to estimate *Quercus ilex*'s spatial distribution in Algeria in order to evaluate the impact of climate change. Using the maximum entropy method (MaxEnt model), the species in the suitable area under climate change scenarios were modelled. Climate, geography, and edaphic factors were the three categories of explanatory variables that were used.

The results showed that the performance of the model used in this study was confirmed by the AUC (area under the curve) value of 0.960. The suitable area of *Quercus ilex* will decrease significantly under the scenarios of RCP2.6 -2070 by 5221,205322 km². The optimal planning strategy sensitizing approach for the preservation the *Quercus ilex* forest and can be created using these results as a decision support tool.

The results demonstrated that the AUC (area under the curve) value of 0.960 supported the model's performance in this examination. Under the RCP2.6 -2070 scenarios, the appropriate area of *Quercus ilex* will decline by 5221,205322 km². Using these data as a decision support tool, the best planning strategy sensitising method for the preservation of the holm oak tree can be developed.

Key words: Climate change, Species distribution modelling, MaxEnt, *Quercus ilex*, Algeria.

Parc National d'El Kala (extrême Nord-Est algérien) : Préservation et protection de la biodiversité

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Abstract

Le Parc National d'El Kala (PNEK) est situé dans l'extrême Nord-Est algérien, il est intégralement inclus dans la wilaya d'El Tarf et possède de grandes réserves d'eau sous forme de zones humides. Celles-ci occupent généralement des zones de transition entre les systèmes aquatiques et terrestres, ce sont des étendues d'eau douce, saumâtre ou salée, permanente ou temporaire, courante ou stagnante, naturelles ou artificielles. Du point de vue des essences forestières, les formations de chêne sont largement dominantes, occupant plus de la moitié de la superficie, La zone d'étude est soumise à un climat méditerranéen caractérisé par une pluviométrie qui peut atteindre 1200 mm/an avec deux saisons l'une sèche et l'autre humide.

Les résultats des analyses physico-chimiques montrent que les eaux sont peu acides et minéralisées. La salinité des eaux oscille entre 0 et 0,5 g/l alors que les fortes teneurs sont enregistrées à l'Est du bassin versant du lac Tonga. Le faciès chimique dominant est chloruré sodique. Les fortes teneurs en PO_4^{3-} dans les eaux naturelles sont liées à la fertilisation intense des terres et à la décomposition de la matière organique des rejets urbains, ce qui favorise l'eutrophisation.

Les actions possibles qui permettent de préserver la biodiversité et agissent en sa faveur sont :

- Limiter la consommation d'espaces et préserver les milieux.
- Protéger les écosystèmes et certaines espèces emblématiques et menacées.
- Permettre la transition de nos modèles de production et de consommation.
- Prendre en compte le lien entre santé et environnement.

Les changements climatiques s'accroissent rapidement, ce qui influe sur les modes de croissance, la disponibilité de la nourriture et les habitudes de migration à un rythme qui dépasse la capacité d'adaptation des écosystèmes et des espèces.

Keywords : Biodiversité ; Zones humides ; Pollution ; Protection ; Environnement

Détermination de la Quantité de Vitamine C et de quelques Sels Minéraux présents dans trois Variétés de Pois Chiche cultivées en Algérie

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Abstract

Le pois chiche fait partie des légumineuses alimentaires les plus cultivées par l'homme, il appartient à la famille des Fabacées. Originaire du pourtour méditerranéen ce dernier occupe une grande place dans nos habitudes alimentaires. Originaire du pourtour méditerranéen, il est emblématique de la cuisine de certains pays comme le Liban. Le pois chiche occupe une grande place dans nos habitudes alimentaires. Il constitue une importante source protéique et se présente comme un substitut aux protéines animales, disponibles à travers les viandes rouges et blanches qui sont difficilement accessibles à de larges couches de la population. Le pois chiche est riche en amidon (glucide complexe), en vitamines et en minéraux. Il est aussi pauvre en graisse et sans cholestérol, ce qui en fait une formidable alternative à la viande. Il s'agit d'un des légumes secs les plus intéressants sur le plan nutritif. C'est pour cela que nous nous sommes tournés vers ce produit et notre travail a porté sur la composition en vitamine C par titration et élément minéraux qui a été faite par la méthode XRF de trois variétés de pois chiche : Tajna, Gap 4 et Flip 84/12. Les résultats étaient respectivement pour les trois variétés de 12,68 % 11,31% 12,25% pour les protéines et de 75ppm 55,4ppm,57,9ppm pour le Fer et de 1422ppm, 1315ppm, 1009ppm pour le Calcium et 510ppm,1314ppm, 1803ppm pour le Magnésium et de 41,7ppm, 44,4ppm 36,6ppm pour le Sodium et de 12426ppm, 10732ppm, 13733ppm pour le Potassium. Pour la vitamine C les résultats étaient comme suit : Tajna 13,07, Gap 4 13,09 et Flip 84/12 13,09. On conclut que les résultats pour les trois variétés se rapprochent et que ces dernières contiennent une bonne quantité en vitamine C et en minéraux. Ces résultats permettent d'introduire les poudres de pois chiche dans des produits alimentaires destinés à la consommation humaine.

Mots-clés : pois chiche, composition physico-chimique, XRF, minéraux, vitamine.

Study of *Salmonella* in vegetables

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Abstract

Salmonella contamination of fresh produce, poses a significant public health concern. This study aimed to investigate the presence and characteristics of *Salmonella* isolates in vegetables, soil and water samples obtained from agricultural sources. A total of 1450 samples were collected from different farms in Bejaia and subjected to microbiological analysis. *Salmonella* spp. were isolated using standard culture methods and confirmed by molecular techniques. The isolates were further characterized for antimicrobial susceptibility, serotype determination, and genetic relatedness using whole genome sequencing. Results revealed the presence of *Salmonella* in 19% of the total samples, indicating a potential risk of foodborne illness associated with vegetables consumption. Antimicrobial susceptibility testing demonstrated varying resistance patterns among the isolates. Serotyping revealed diverse *Salmonella* serotypes, suggesting multiple contamination sources. Molecular analysis indicated genetic diversity among the isolates, with some strains showing close relatedness to clinical isolates. These findings underscore the importance of implementing stringent food safety measures throughout the vegetables production and distribution chain to mitigate the risk of *Salmonella* contamination and subsequent foodborne outbreaks.

Keywords: *Salmonella*, antimicrobial resistance, vegetables, agricultural environments, genotypic characterization, food safety

Sustainable Valorization of Agricultural By-products for Biodiversity Protection

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Abstract:

Biotechnological advancements offer promising solutions for biodiversity preservation, especially in fragile ecosystems. This study investigates the potential of agricultural by-products, particularly olive pomace, through the extraction and analysis of bioactive compounds. These by-products, often regarded as waste, contain phenolic compounds with antioxidant and antimicrobial properties that can be leveraged for ecological conservation. Using sustainable extraction methods and advanced analytical techniques, we aim to demonstrate how these bioactive compounds can contribute to reducing the environmental impact of agricultural production. By integrating these insights into a strategy for waste valorization, we propose a biotechnological approach to preserve biodiversity while promoting sustainable resource management.

Keywords: Biodiversity, Biotechnology, Olive Pomace, Bioactive Compounds, Ecosystem Preservation, By-product Valorization

Le Figuier De Barbarie (*Opuntia ficus indica*)

Valorisation et Perspective pour Le Développement Rural en zone

Steppique de l'Est Algérien

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Résumé

Le Figuier de Barbarie (*Opuntia ficus indica*) offre de nombreux avantages, notamment comme réserve d'eau, source de nourriture pour l'homme et fourrage pour les animaux. Il joue un rôle crucial dans la lutte contre le changement climatique en Algérie, un pays dont l'écosystème fragile est affecté par la surexploitation des ressources naturelles. Depuis les années 1970, le MADR a initié des programmes pour valoriser les réserves fourragères, en favorisant la plantation d'espèces adaptées aux conditions arides. L'étude menée dans la région nord-est de Tébessa, sur trois sites (HenchirLahdid, OuledWaar et OuledMebarek), a examiné le potentiel de rendement du figuier de Barbarie.

La superficie moyenne cultivée est inférieure à un hectare, avec 80% des exploitations ayant des parcelles de cette taille. Les parcelles, souvent rectangulaires, sont influencées par le morcellement suite aux héritages et l'accessibilité. L'espacement des plants varie de 1 à 5 mètres, avec une moyenne de 2,8 mètres. Le poids moyen des fruits par cladode (MFWC) dépend de leur largeur : ceux de 15 à 18 cm pèsent 102 à 110 g, tandis que ceux de plus de 35 cm atteignent 145 g. En outre, le nombre de graines viables et les conditions d'entretien influencent le poids des fruits, qui varie également selon les cultivars et le cycle de croissance. Au site de HenchirLahdid, le nombre moyen de graines par fruit est de 291. De cela, un programme de développement visant à promouvoir la culture du figuier de Barbarie doit être mise en place, en intégrant l'élevage et la protection de l'environnement tout en tenant compte des besoins humains. Il est essentiel de mener des actions de vulgarisation, de soutien et de sensibilisation pour encourager les plantations maraîchères et l'utilisation des jus de fruits, des jeunes cladodes et de leurs dérivés. L'utilisation des cladodes et des résidus pour l'alimentation du bétail doit également être favorisée. Cette culture peut bénéficier à toutes les populations, indépendamment de leur niveau de vie, et soutenir l'activité économique dans les zones steppiques, marginales et montagneuses. La mise en œuvre de ce programme devrait s'inscrire dans un aménagement intégré adapté à chaque région.

Mot clé : superficie; exploitations; espacement; valorisation; graines; fruits

Characterization of Vine Biodiversity in Khenchela region (North-East Algeria) through a Multidimensional Approach: Implications for Management and Conservation

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Abstract :

The Algerian vineyard presents an interesting situation where vineyard crops based on local varieties coexist, but with generally uncertain potential. To determine the characterization of autochthonous grapevine varieties, present in the region of Khenchela (North-East Algeria), we examined the use of the MARTINEZ and GRENAN (1999) method using ampelographic descriptors from the OIV (inter-national grapevine organization). This method aims to quickly and clearly visualize the leaf morphology of a grape variety in order to identify it. A principal component analysis was used to identify the most discriminating descriptors, notably the length and angle of the veins, the length and width of the teeth and the opening of the petiolar sinus. Cluster analysis was used to group cultivars into several categories based on their similarities, assuming that they are synonymous and related. The results obtained from this study encourage us to develop other grape varieties threatened with extinction in this neglected region, and to contribute to the conservation of genetic resources of cultivated and indigenous grape varieties in Algeria.

Keywords: vine; varieties; ampelography; conservation; indigenous.

Harnessing *Azolla pinnata*: Innovations in Sustainable Agriculture and Aquaculture

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Abstract

The increasing demand for sustainable agricultural and aquacultural practices calls for innovative solutions. This study investigates the potential of *Azolla pinnata*, a nitrogen-fixing aquatic fern, across multiple applications. We optimized *Azolla* cultivation by evaluating the effects of temperature and shading on biomass production, finding that moderate shading (70%) and slightly higher water temperatures (25-27.7°C) created the most favorable conditions for growth. As a biofertilizer, *Azolla* enhanced plant height, leaf number, and leaf size in pepper plants (*Capsicum annuum*) when applied at 10% and 20% concentrations. Additionally, *Azolla* proved effective in wastewater treatment, reducing pH from 8.1 to 7.14, electrical conductivity (EC) from 2.1 to 1.39 mS/cm, total dissolved solids (TDS) from 1.155 to 0.787 ppt, and salinity from 1.344 to 0.966 ppt over 30 days. Future research will explore the incorporation of *Azolla* into tilapia diets to assess its effects on fish health and growth. This study highlights the versatility of *Azolla pinnata* in promoting sustainable practices in both agriculture and aquaculture, contributing to environmental sustainability and food security.

Keywords: *Azolla pinnata*, Sustainable agriculture, Biofertilizer, Wastewater treatment, Aquaculture.

Halotolerant phosphate solubilizing bacteria improve antioxidant systems and photosynthetic activity of cultivated barley under salinity

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Abstract

Different approaches have been proposed and adopted to minimize the adverse effects of salt stress on plant development and productivity. Among the strategies reported is the, inoculation with plant-growth-promoting rhizobacteria (PGPR). This work aims to investigate the effect of inoculation by three phosphorus solubilizing bacteria (PSB) on the growth and the development of barley (*Hordeum vulgare*) grown in the presence of salt (250 mM NaCl). Inoculation with the strains *Bacillus subtilis* and *Pseudomonas brassicacearum* stimulates the vegetative development of this local variety Rihane and improves the photosynthetic activity and consequently the biomass and length of the shoots and roots. Our results from the evaluation of the effects of inoculation by PSB on oxidative metabolism showed that inoculation with *Pseudomonas brassicacearum* and especially with *Bacillus subtilis* are the most effective for decreasing the production of reactive oxygen species (H₂O₂) by (-22%) and (-50%) respectively; and decreasing MDA levels by 70%, this result is associated with an activation of antioxidant defense system. In fact, both *Bacillus subtilis* and *Pseudomonas brassicacearum* strains increased catalase (CAT) activity by (+74%) and (+40%) respectively, in addition PSB enhanced superoxide dismutase (SOD) activity. In conclusion, halotolerant phosphate solubilizing bacteria inoculation repairs oxidative damages by preventing ROS accumulation and amplifying antioxidant systems under salt stress.

Keywords: Barley, PGP bacteria, salinity, plant growth, photosynthetic activity, oxidative metabolism.

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